

APPROACH

**Advanced Photonic PRocesses for novel sOlar energy
hArvesting teCHnologies**

Deliverable 3.5

D3.5 Human Capital of Excellence

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Deliverable due date: 30 November 2025

Actual submission date: 30 November 2025

Version: 1.0

This project receives funding in the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

Document Control Page	
Title	D35Human Capital of Excellence
Creator	VAMK
Description	Report on human capital of excellence covering the period of June 2023 (month 1) and November 2025 (month 30)
Creation date	27 Nov 2025
Type	Report
Language	English
Audience	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> public <input type="checkbox"/> confidential
Review status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> W P leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator accepted

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The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the APPROACH project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.

I. Abstract

Deliverable D3.5, entitled 'Human Capital Excellence', details the measures that have been implemented from June 2023 to November 2025 (30 months) with the objective of positively impacting human capital excellence. The Deliverable D3.5 is part of the Work Package (WP) 3. A variety of actions were carried out with the primary objective of fostering the development of human capital excellence among young talents in the domain of solar energy harvesting technologies to establish the necessary frameworks and conditions that facilitate training and talent development. The participants in the WP3 included such as heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers, many of which also represented young talents themselves. The activities delivered in WP3 encompassed the development of human capital excellence, addressing such areas as training in grant applications and the improvement of project management skills, as well as open science and data management. Moreover, an investigation was conducted into contemporary knowledge-sharing methodologies and strategies for their implementation, and reflection on leadership, team management, administration and management aspects for building human capital excellence.

2. Introduction

Human capital excellence is a practice aimed at improving the performance of employees. In this case, it focuses on research talent in the solar energy harvesting sector, as well as on heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers.

This deliverable observes the impact of the training workshops, research and other activities provided in Work Package 3 of the APPROACH project, and their ability to contribute to increasing human capital excellence. Many workshops do not address human capital excellence directly but instead provide knowledge in different areas. These include training in open science, data management, grant writing, knowledge sharing and management skills improvement for researchers and innovators. The aim is to build participants' capacities and knowledge to leverage their potential as researchers, heads of research and project managers. Such areas of knowledge form an integral part of researchers' work. In addition, this document will consider the structural elements involved in developing human capital and the excellence of research talent, including elements related to administration, management and strategy.

3. Towards human capital excellence

The development of human capital excellence in the APPROACH project is built on three layers:

1. Deliverable 3.1. Training needs analysis. The purpose of this deliverable was to investigate the knowledge, skills and abilities of researchers and innovators should possess to determine the types of training to which they were to be addressed. ApproachComp, a framework of competences for researchers on of solar energy harvesting technology sectors was created of the results. This deliverable, not part of D3.5, created the fundamentals for the upcoming activities in the project.
2. Deliverables 3.2 - 3.4. These deliverables reported on the training activities and workshops implemented in Work Package 3.
3. Deliverable 3.5. Human capital excellence, this deliverable, forms the third dimension of the trinity of activity areas in the WP3. It focuses on impact creation through strategy, training of heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers especially, open Science and data management, Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee Process, and grant applications, thus, how to excel the talents.

In addition, technical excellence of the talents is built on Work Package 2, Research & Innovation Excellence.

The following chapters delineate the activities of Work Package 3, which focused on promoting human capital excellence in young talents especially through heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers, many of which also represented young talents themselves.

3.1 Impact through training administrators and managers, leadership and team management

The APPROACH consortium launched a structured Workshop Series designed to strengthen research administration, leadership, communication, and team management across participating organisations. The series responded directly to the project's objectives under Task 3.2 'Administrators and Managers training' and Task 3.6 'Leadership and Team Management' as part of the work package 3, 'Human Capital of Excellence'. There grew into a capacity-building mechanism within the project. Each workshop addressed practical operational challenges that research managers and team leaders face in multi-partner and multi-project environments, drawing on peer learning, case analysis, and interactive exercises. The contributions span from foundational administrative practices to advanced team-

communication strategies, creating a coherent training pathway for administrators, project managers and unit leaders, to help them support excelling of human capital.

The overarching themes of the workshops demonstrated consistency across both tasks; however, a notable distinction emerged in the focal points of each. Task 3.2 placed significant emphasis on management and administrative aspect, while Task 3.6 adopted a more human-centred approach, prioritising individual needs and experiences. Consequently, both perspectives were discussed around the same set of themes, thus creating a holistic perspective of the various challenges, good practices and solutions. The workshops were organised by FORTH and VAMK, while the other partners, IMEC, Novinano, OHK, PDoT, Solaronix, TSNUK and UPOL, also joined the workshops. Sixteen heads of units and research groups, team leaders and project managers participated in the workshops according to their availability, resulting in varying levels of participation.

The themes of the workshops were:

1. **Workshop 1 organised 13th March 2025:** Managing multiple projects with limited resources. How to maintain consistent quality throughout.
2. **Workshop 2 organised 15th April 2025:** Struggling with team communication issues: How to prevent scheduling conflicts and delays. Part 1.
3. **Workshop 3 organised 24th June 2025:** Factors considered for an efficient filing system in your organization: Examples of timesheets
4. **Workshop 4 organised 1st September 2025:** Struggling with the team communication issues. How to prevent scheduling conflicts and delays - Part 2.
5. **Workshop 5 organised 8th October 2025:** “Juggling Several Projects at Once: How to Stay Organised”. This included ‘Factors considered for an efficient filing system in your organisation.’

An additional, supplementary workshop will be organised on 3rd December 2025.

Impact and assessment

The central methods for impact creation and assessment were peer learning and good practices. Peer learning is a communicative and collaborative method, that allowed sharing information and personal perspectives for a specific purpose or knowledge, attitudes or habits, and for discussion. while individually building on their existing knowledge, experiences, mental structures and cultural background. (Boud, D., Cohen, R., & Sampson, J., 1999; Karolinska Institutet, 2025; Keerthirathne, 2020; Zdzislaw Polkowski, Rajendrasinh Jadeja, Nitul Dutta, 2020). During the workshops, the

participants engaged in a reciprocal learning process through sharing good practices. The assessment consisted of a discussion of the presented practices while connecting them to other practices, and consequently, through this process, identification of good practices in general, and as subjects of learning and potential further implementation. The impact was created by increasing knowledge of different practices, linking the presented ideas to what had already been learnt, and practical benefit for daily work. The basis for further and long-term impact was established through the preparation of the presentations for sharing them via online channels.

In addition, a **Miro board** was prepared for collecting and summarising information to identify good practices through a shared idea-based assessment (<https://miro.com>). Miro is an online platform that enables collaborative activities such as ideation using virtual sticky notes. The data collection was to happen in small groups and discussed together for practice assessment. Eventually, discussions with the entire group of participants replaced the use of Miro.

The impact of the workshops can be divided into the perspectives of management and administration aspects, as well as individual, human-centred and leadership aspects. These dimensions are closely intertwined, supporting each other. The immediate impact is created to the workshop participants as immediate increase of knowledge while the long-term impact will also benefit the talents, through the implemented practices as human capital excellence of the talents. Continuous assessment of the practices is advised and to be based on quality management specific for each area of activity.

Workshop 1: Impact creation of human capital excellence in the topic ‘Managing multiple projects with limited resources. How to maintain consistent quality throughout.’ in the dimension of **management and administration**, highlighted elements such as:

- Elements that organise and calm the work at organisational and individual levels, including work time allocation by projects to avoid overlap and inefficiencies, breaking down projects into manageable tasks, and managing own worktime with different tools.
- Resources allocation and adaptability, including optimising human resources, leveraging automatisations, outsourcing when needed, setting realistic deadlines, and adapting promptly to resource constraints.
- Effective communication, for instance, about the project and work situations, processes, practices, changes, and task to do.
- Quality management.

Addressing such issues liberates time for leveraging human capital excellence. Besides trickling-down the positive effects of the management level to human-level, the suggestions for the **leadership and**

human-centred dimension included elements linked to maintaining team morale, encouraging learning, flexibility in schedules, and burnout prevention.

Workshop 2: Impact creation of human capital excellence in the topic of ‘Struggling with team communication issues: How to prevent scheduling conflicts and delays. Part 1.’ in the dimension of **management and administration**, highlighted elements such as:

- Purposeful and clear communication according to the objective and scope with the right amount of information.
- Setting clear roles, responsibilities and authority while avoiding ambiguity in accountability, overlapping responsibilities, lack of defined authority and siloed working.
- Use of right tools for communication, a communication plan and communication channels.
- Application of principles and practices for conflict resolution and priorities included.

The application of these elements saves time and facilitates **leadership processes and a human-centred approach**. They also help to address cultural differences, whether organisational or national, including varying work ethics and norms, communication styles, decision-making processes, and attitudes towards conflict, trust, and relationship building. For example, they help to prevent burnout.

Workshop 3: Impact creation of human capital excellence in the topic ‘Factors considered for an efficient filing system in your organization: Examples of time sheets’ in the dimension of **management and administration**, highlighted elements such as:

- Strengthening administrative infrastructure.
- Organising information: Filing system, centralised repositories, documented folder hierarchies, metadata and indexing strategies, clear access-management procedures, and for files using clear, consistent filenames (include project acronym/ID, WP number, date, version) – e.g. PROJ123_WP2_DataAnalysis_v1.0.docx.
- Timesheets and work time follow-up built in organisations.

These cannot be properly implemented without effective leadership and a human-centred approach. It is therefore advisable to ensure that everyone receives support with administrative matters and is provided with the appropriate instructions.

Workshop 4: Impact creation of human capital excellence in the topic of ‘Struggling with the team communication issues. How to prevent scheduling conflicts and delays - Part 2’ identified four main areas of attention: people-related issues, organisatory issues, technical and legal issues, and other issues.

The organisatory and technical and legal issues were mostly covered the dimension of **management and administration**. **These included such as** organisatory issues are at place, descriptions and instruction, structure, usability of systems, and use of processes, and cybersecurity or access-related issues for legal issues. This fosters trust in the process at organisational and human levels, thereby facilitating the allocation of resources and time to the development of human capital excellence.

However, it cannot be achieved without **leadership and a human-centred dimension** that focuses on people-related issues. People-related issues include different levels of experience and background requiring different leadership approaches. For example, this applies when navigating between academia and business or when working with people with physical conditions and disabilities, including those who are neuroatypical.

The issue of 'noise' has been identified as a factor that hinders the ability to focus on work and impedes talent development. These were also identified as being essential in creating impact.

Workshop 5: For impact creation of human capital excellence in the topic of 'Juggling Several Projects at Once: How to Stay Organised' was explored through a variety of scenarios, covering both management and administration, and leadership and human-centred dimensions. These dimensions are intricately interwoven to form a complex, multifaceted landscape. The dimensions discussed cover organisational, project and individual levels. These were reflected against the reality of managing multiple projects and common challenges that create chaos. Once more, the fundamental elements for facilitating the implementation of work, leadership, people-oriented aspects, delegation and team structures were identified as structure-building, priority-setting, tools, communication and functional administration and management.

As was confirmed by all five workshops, in order to create a positive impact on human capital excellence, it is essential that both managerial and administrative, as well as leadership and human-centred aspects, are considered. It was determined that these aspects are most effective when intertwined in a balanced manner. A well-structured and effective managerial and administrative function is conducive to the establishment of foundations that enable teams and individuals to thrive in projects and in work, particularly when supported by leadership and with consideration of various aspects of the human dimension, such as culture. It is therefore imperative that talents, i.e. young researchers, develop comprehension and competences in both dimensions.

The presentations of the workshops are available in the Annex 1 of this deliverable.

3.2 Impact through training in grant applications and improvement of project management skills for researchers and innovators

Training in grant writing and improvement of project management skills were essential for human capital excellence. Grant writing is an elemental part of researchers and innovators work. The main themes for the workshops are application hard skills mentoring, application idea mentoring profiting, project workflow management, and mentoring. Two main training activities can be highlighted.

1. Prague March 2025

Within the context of an event in Prague 27th – 28th March 2025 including, for instance, training for talents, three training workshops were held related to grant applications and improvement of project management skills for researchers and innovators.

As the first one, the presentation 'Designing Scientific Project Frameworks That Win: Strategies for Horizon Europe applications' at the workshop in Prague, in March 2025, and presented by Andrea Nogová, served as a fundamental starting point for grant application training on which it is easier to build further training on grant applications. The workshop presented the Horizon Europe 9th Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021 –2027) as whole from a very practical point of view, including the key expectations and the three key pillars that address both individual researchers and organisations. Evaluation and framework of a project proposal were also examined, as well as the key points to consider and Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA) funding.

The second presentation by Aristeides Bakandritsos focused on 'How to design an appealing scientific project proposal' created a logical next step for the process. It detailed with care and from a practical point of view '1. How to approach the proposal writing,', '2. How to compose a strong consortium', and '3. How to be convincing in terms of the KPIs' (KPI = key performance indicators).

The third presentation provided advice for 'Strategies For Researchers for Sustainable Success' by Eirini Ioannou focused on Aspects of Sustainable Success in Research, Part I: Working and Collaborating effectively and Part II: Goal Setting & Time Management.

The three workshops imparted fundamental skills, knowledge, information and tacit knowledge on research funding types, application and project management, and information on European opportunities at individual, team and organisational levels. The information provided was concrete, and thus it was highly likely that it would eliminate any hindering factors that might have impeded progress towards the application of European funding. The principles presented at the workshops can be easily adapted to national contexts, thus increasing their impact due to their high exploitation potential. It is reasonable to hypothesise that the workshops will have a high probability of exerting a

positive influence on the development of the participants' skills, knowledge and competencies, and consequently on the enhancement of human capital excellence.

The presentations are available in the Annex 2.

2. Training by IMEC in December 2025

The third part of training in grant applications and improvement of project management skills for researchers and innovators is scheduled to take place in December 2025. This component will be administered by IMEC.

3.3 Impact through open science and data management

Three activities were implemented under the task of Open Science and Data management Training (Task 3.4), a survey and two workshops.

1. Research of open science and data management challenges and opportunities

The objective of the research, which was performed as a survey, was to identify and benchmark the experiences, preferences, and situations related to **open science and data management** among various stakeholder groups, including scientists, SME representatives, academics, policymakers, the general public, and other relevant actors from diverse sectors, such as other professionals engaged in research, education, and innovation-related activities, in the partner countries Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, Greece, Ukraine, and Switzerland. A number of responses were received from various other countries as well. A total of 175 participants completed the questionnaire. The survey instrument was administered via the Webropol platform.

The responses yielded valuable insights into the experiences, perceptions, and training needs related to open science and data management. The survey thus also served the function of an assessment of the extant methodologies pertaining to these subjects, in addition to the manner of their utilisation by end-users and other relevant parties. The European Commission has underscored the significance of open science for research and innovation, characterising it as a paradigm that fosters transparency and collaboration (European Commission, 2016), as also that of data management, which involves the processes of storing, organising, and maintaining research data (OECD, 2017). The investigation of experiences, perceptions, and training needs related to these with the particular focus on the application of these concepts in solar energy harvesting technology research has the potential to promote human capital excellence in the respective field through increased information in the form of insights, planned training, and the potential application of these methods by end-users and other stakeholders.

The main areas of investigation were Awareness and Understanding of Open Science, Current Practices in Data Management, Current Practices in Data Management, Perceived Benefits and Opportunities, and Training Needs and Participation Preferences.

The survey results indicated a predominantly favourable attitude towards open science and data management among the respondents, as well as a strong motivation to learn more about these concepts and to use them in their own activity. Moreover, participation in a variety of initiatives was viewed in a negative light. However, a substantial variation was observed in terms of awareness and comprehension of these concepts, as well as their practical implementation, which remained limited. A significant

proportion of survey respondents indicated a lack of requisite training, over 50%, reported that of formal education, institutional guidance, or tools for open science and data management, which they reported as a hindrance to the integration of these practices into their daily work. Furthermore, lack of clearly defined internal policies pertaining to data management or compliance was observed in a significant proportion of the organisations surveyed. This further impacts on the level of familiarity with the FAIR data principles, which remains limited and inconsistent. In addition to the aforementioned barriers, time constraints, a lack of incentives, and limited infrastructure also hinder the proper application of open science and data management.

The following recommendations are derived from the survey findings and are designed to address the skills, open science and data management issues. These recommendations, herewith presented as direct quotation from the survey report created by the APPROACH consortium, include elements that address both personal and institutional factors that inhibit engagement.

- First, **awareness and communication** around open science should be enhanced. Greater dissemination of information about EU and national policies, as well as visibility of successful case studies and good practices, can help bridge existing knowledge gaps. Consistent communication strategies can also strengthen engagement among stakeholders across research, business, and policy sectors.
- Second, **training and capacity building** should be expanded and diversified. A modular training program that includes topics such as FAIR data principles, open access publishing, ethical data handling, and repository use would help address the uneven distribution of knowledge. The delivery of training should prioritize flexibility through self-paced online courses, webinars, and short video-based materials that accommodate time constraints. Practical, hands-on exercises and case-based examples should be incorporated to reinforce learning outcomes and promote applicability to participants' professional contexts.
- Third, **institutional support and infrastructure** should be improved. Organizations should be encouraged to adopt standardized internal policies for data management and compliance, and to integrate open-source tools such as Zenodo or the Open Science Framework (Foster & Deardorff, 2017) into their daily workflows. Providing access to technical assistance and guidance on metadata standards and repository management would facilitate consistency and reliability in data handling practices.
- Fourth, it is important to **create meaningful incentives** for participation in open science. Recognition of open data contributions in performance evaluations, career progression, and research funding schemes would encourage wider engagement. Establishing reward

mechanisms or small grants for open data initiatives could further motivate both individuals and institutions to participate.

- Finally, a **collaborative and inclusive approach** should be fostered. Researchers, SMEs, policymakers, and educators should be actively involved in co-developing training materials, tools, and guidelines to ensure relevance across sectors. Promoting cross-sector collaboration can bridge the gap between academic and business perspectives, while pilot projects and feedback loops within the APPROACH framework can ensure continuous improvement and validation of tools and training resources.

The findings provide substantial support for a dual training approach encompassing both open science and data management, comprising a segment dedicated to conceptual understanding and another to practical application. This would not only address the strengthening of scientific excellence, societal impact and transparent research culture in Europe, but would also facilitate the development of key competences of excellence in researchers.

The full report is available in the Annex 5 of this deliverable.

2.. Workshop 1: ‘Unlock The Power of your Data ‘

The workshop ‘Unlock The Power of your Data’ was part of the concrete and practical solutions for open science and data management. It was presented by Information Management Officer Bilal Naffaa from IMEC. It was organised as part of the webinar ‘Workshop on Catalyzing Innovation: Infrastructure, Projects & People – Part 1’ on 28 May 2025, 14:00–16:00 CEST.

The workshop provided an introduction to the fundamental principles of data management and open science in a manner that was both comprehensive and accessible, thereby addressing the identified deficit in training in these subjects. The presentation contained print screens that created a new layer, which is expected to assist researchers using the presented systems and thereby lower the threshold of usage of them. The workshop also presented Data Management Plan (DPM), the concept of metadata, and, as an example, the data storage system Zenodo, and provided step-by-step guidance in an educative manner on how to use Zenodo, thus enabling the participants to start using it. The materials are available in Annex 3.

2.. Workshop 2: ‘ Open Science and Open Data‘

CATRIN organised a virtual workshop on ‘Open Science and Open Data’ on Wednesday, 29 October 2025, at 9:30 CET. The workshop was given by Jakub Navařík, an expert in the field. In addition to

the principles of open data, the FAIR principle was examined in depth at each stage of the study. The materials are available in Annex 4.

The two workshops on open science and data management provided a comprehensive overview of the fundamental principles underpinning these themes. The selection of perspectives complemented each other and provided necessary repetition on open science as well. The workshops were characterised by clarity and pragmatism, thus addressing the necessity for training in data management and open science. Taking especially into account researchers in solar energy harvesting sectors, the division of data management and FAIR principles was made into laboratory approach and publication approach. In order to ensure a long-term impact, it is recommended that these materials be made freely available to young researchers, with the potential to develop more in-depth or wide-ranging training and conceptual frameworks based on them.

3.4 Impact through knowledge-sharing and Interactive employee process

Knowledge-sharing and interactive employee processes are of paramount importance in the creation of impact and the development of human capital of excellence. The primary dimensions pertain to the subject-specific concerns and cross-cutting elements that are largely consistent across various subjects and areas. These elements may include premises, tools, strategies, and internal rules, as well as communication principles. This chapter delineates the activities of the Approaches Task 3.5 Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee Process, which comprises the following:

1. Investigation of current knowledge-sharing methods and team/ employee processes.
2. Piloting knowledge-sharing in a workshop.
3. Creating a strategy document based on the findings from the investigation and piloting workshop.

Investigation

The objective of the investigation was to identify good knowledge sharing practice and interactive employee processes through a survey and desktop research. The investigation focused on identifying organisational enablers, methods and digital tools that support employee interaction and the sharing of experiences, expertise, ideas, and information. The results were used to develop a piloting workshop on knowledge-sharing practices and a strategy document. Altogether 137 researchers in the field of technology from Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, Greece, Switzerland and Ukraine responded to the survey. The results were collated to a report that describes the approach to data collection, presents and synthesises the findings from the survey, provides ideas and suggestions for enhancing knowledge-sharing, and offers recommendations for organisations to strengthen knowledge-sharing practices. The data collection took place in autumn 2025 and was extended due to a low response rate.

The primary findings indicated substantial heterogeneity in organisational methodologies pertaining for knowledge-sharing. The technical infrastructure comprising structured methods and widely adopted

digital tools were well established. The challenges arise from such variables as cultural factors, organisational and national, thus also habits and norms, human factors, and formal enablers, diversifying knowledge-sharing methods, and expanding the use of interactive technologies. In order to adequately address the practices of knowledge-sharing and interactive employee processes, with the objective of creating impact and promoting human capital excellence, it is necessary to address the factors that may compromise the effectiveness of knowledge-sharing practices.

Three critical knowledge-sharing enablers emerged from the data, that an organisation should address. These are such as psychological safety and a trust-based environment, that was regarded to be foundational for any knowledge-sharing initiative and impacting to other two emerged factors. The second emergent element was digital tools, with such platforms as Microsoft Teams, SharePoint and Miro being notable examples. In addition to facilitating communication in general and in geographically dispersed projects, these technologies are also imperative for the adaptation of hybrid and remote work models. Thirdly, establishing a balance between formal and informal mechanisms promotes knowledge-sharing and may also contribute positively to innovation. As means, the report lists such as workshops, mentoring programs, and centralised repositories that provide consistency and accessibility, and on the other hand informal interactions and spontaneous discussions.

Furthermore, in order to ensure the effective impact and utilisation of human capital excellence through the implementation of Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee Process, it is essential to ensure the effective application of leadership and change management within the organisational processes.

The piloting knowledge workshop

The purpose of the workshop was twofold: firstly, to act as a pilot to assess the outcomes of the desk-based research; and secondly, to collect other methods and ideas for knowledge-sharing processes. The workshop titled 'Workshop for Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee - How to become a knowledge-sharing organisation' was organised on 18th November 2025 using Microsoft Teams. A total of 18 participants from Belgium, Finland, and Greece participated in the workshop. Eight participants were actively engaged in the workshop.

Collecting other methods was facilitated by a Miro board (<https://miro.com/>). The participants were initially divided into groups; however, due to the low level of participation, all participants were incorporated into a single group. The purpose was to understand how organisational culture, tools, and

working methods influence knowledge-sharing across the participating countries to identify cross-organisational insights, highlight common needs, to compare these to the outcomes of the desk research, and outline practical recommendations to support a stronger, more systematic knowledge-sharing environment. The collaborative tasks were:

- Task 1: Explore cultural enablers and barriers to knowledge-sharing

The role of structured activities, organisational arrangements in facilitating knowledge exchange, and the benefits such as preventing knowledge loss, accelerating decision-making, and supporting continuous improvement were examined.

- Task 2: Examine current tools and methods, identify challenges, and propose improvements

Findings from the survey were presented. As the most effective tools and methods were mentioned, the following were highlighted as top-rated: structured and interactive methods such as meetings, training, workshops, and brainstorming. In contrast, creative techniques were found to be less commonly used.

The results of the workshop align with the findings of the desk research. The implementation of structured processes and the cultivation of a supportive knowledge-sharing culture are pivotal in demonstrating the efficacy of structured practices and documentation systems in fostering enhanced knowledge-sharing and cooperation. It is imperative to provide formal and structured opportunities and platforms to which all individuals have access, in addition to systems to support information management. This approach fosters reliability and consistency in communication.

In the context of knowledge-sharing tools and methods, the most prevalent challenges encountered by users primarily pertain to the scarcity of time to familiarise themselves with the tools and methods, the ambiguity of expectations regarding tool usage, and the absence of structured workflows. Consequently, rather than utilising the tools to their advantage, there is a possibility that they may, in fact, result in an increased burden. It became evident that simply providing tools and methods is not enough.

It is imperative that any measures implemented with the objective of encouraging the use of tools address the underlying causes of the issue in question. Furthermore, such measures must be effective in reducing any existing confusion. It is imperative that the process is rendered uncomplicated, thereby ensuring that the tools are utilised for their designated purpose without the necessity of excessive attention.

Among the identified suggestions are consistency, the culture of transparency, information, and standardisation of tools and methods within teams can work as a starting point. In addition, the threshold of using them may further reduce when providing accessible training and for instance

templates to use them. Tools should be easy to find in centralised repositories and time should be allocated for starting to use them.

The following suggestions have been identified: consistency, the culture of transparency, information, and standardisation of tools and methods within teams. These could be considered as a starting point. Furthermore, the threshold for their utilisation may be reduced through the provision of accessible training and templates. It is imperative that tools are readily accessible in centralised repositories, and that time is allocated for learning how to use tools.

The strategy document

A strategy document was formulated on the basis of the insights obtained from the investigation and the workshop. The document synthesises the insights gained throughout the process. The objective of the programme is to provide a framework for enhancing knowledge-sharing among employees, both within individual teams and across organisational boundaries. It is designed to establish guidelines for the implementation of effective practices and to facilitate the integration of organisational enablers, methodologies, and digital tools that promote interaction and the exchange of experiences, expertise, ideas, and information.

The strategy document is divided into five parts. The first part discusses what knowledge-sharing is and emphasises its role in organisational learning, innovation, and performance, distinguishing between explicit and tacit knowledge. It also examines enablers and barriers to knowledge sharing. The second part examines the factors that facilitate knowledge-sharing within organisations. These factors include formal and informal practices, leadership, incentives, tools, management systems and organisational processes. This approach incorporates behavioural indicators and organisational metrics. The third part, entitled 'Good Knowledge Sharing Practices', showcases examples identified through surveys and workshops within the APPROACH project. These combine digital tools with social and collaborative methods to foster knowledge flow. The dimension incorporates cultural factors that influence success and offers recommendations for creating environments where knowledge-sharing thrives. The fourth part 'Summing Up: Becoming a Knowledge Sharing Organisation' summarises the findings and provides actionable recommendations for integrating knowledge-sharing as a sustainable part of organisational life.

The key insights and lessons learnt can be summarised

The exchange of knowledge has been demonstrated to be of significant benefit to an organisation. The capacity of an organisation to facilitate the exchange of tacit knowledge, mobilise the knowledge, skills

and experiences of its workforce, and to support the process of transforming these into new ideas, improved practices and impactful research outcomes is of paramount importance. It is evident that there is a direct link to the innovation capacity of the organisation in question.

Becoming a knowledge-sharing organisation requires activities to be built from three perspectives: 1) Focusing on strategic and cultural transformation, utilising leadership; 2) Creating trust-based relationships and practices, psychological safety, and motivational mechanisms and enable the free flow of ideas and expertise; and 3) Selecting and implementing the right tools and processes, while providing training in their use. Including organisational clarity, supportive leadership, transparency, consistent expectations and shared goals is essential to motivate and encourage employees through the process.

Transparent communication should aim to eliminate a lack of reciprocity, the hoarding of knowledge, the withholding of information, and even sabotage of information. This is particularly important when employees perceive knowledge-sharing as a threat to their status or job security.

Robust knowledge flows are required for the exchange of both tacit and explicit knowledge across teams and organisational boundaries, as well as for interpersonal communication. These methods should be interactive and socially grounded. Examples of such activities include meetings, workshops, brainstorming sessions, mentoring, training and lessons learned. These processes also enhance psychological safety.

Digital infrastructures, including email, collaboration platforms and document management systems, should be integrated into knowledge-sharing processes. Employees require clear information regarding the intended use of these systems, their availability, and the method for utilising them.

It is imperative that leadership is leveraged to facilitate open knowledge-sharing processes, thereby providing guidance through periods of change and setting an example. This may be achieved by demonstrating openness, acknowledging mistakes, and fostering dialogue.

It is imperative that knowledge-sharing systems and processes are universally accessible and meticulously documented. This requires the capacity to recognise knowledge-sharing behaviours, promoting knowledge-sharing policies, good documentation and shared repositories, internal communication about the tools, eliminating internal barriers, procedural clarity and integrating it into strategies long-term instead of ad-hoc activities. Informal information-sharing practices may promote cultural learning to normalise knowledge exchange.

Lastly, an organisation should clearly transmit its communication and knowledge-sharing practices to its employees. This helps employees share information, reduces silos, reinforces positive behaviour, and ultimately benefits the organisation.

Strategic recommendations for building a knowledge sharing organisation

Finally, the strategy document presents strategic recommendations for building a knowledge-sharing organization. It is presented herewith below with the respective figure and descriptions from the strategy document directly transferred as such onto this deliverable.

Figure 1 Knowledge Sharing Organisation

1. **Embed knowledge sharing into organisational culture:** Organisations should promote psychological safety and trust through leadership behaviours, peer-support mechanisms and clear communication. Leaders play a critical role by modelling openness, encouraging dialogue and linking knowledge sharing explicitly to organisational success. A culture grounded in trust, fairness and recognition reduces the risk of knowledge hoarding or withholding and supports the view of knowledge as a collective asset rather than individual property.
2. **Establish structured and repeatable processes:** Findings across data sources highlight the need for consistent procedures for capturing, sharing and applying knowledge. Integrating reflection, documentation and lessons-learned discussions into routine workflows helps ensure that knowledge exchange becomes a regular practice. In some countries, workshop participants noted that the absence of such structured methods hinders consistent knowledge flow

- demonstrating that even small procedural improvements can lead to meaningful change. Standard templates, meeting structures and shared routines strengthen clarity and reduce reliance on informal and inconsistent practices.
3. **Develop centralised and coherent knowledge repositories:** Fragmentation of information across multiple platforms or private storage locations emerged as a common challenge. Organisations benefit from centralised, user-friendly repositories supported by clear conventions for naming, storing and accessing documents. In some contexts, disciplined use of shared spaces has significantly improved accessibility and reliability of organisational knowledge. Such repositories also ensure equitable access to information across teams and roles and create a durable foundation for organisational memory.
 4. **Strengthen digital tool competence and coherence:** While organisations have access to numerous digital tools, survey results show challenges related to tool overload, inconsistent usage and insufficient training. Offering continuous, accessible support, such as short training sessions, onboarding packages or micro-learning materials, helps ensure that all employees can use tools effectively and confidently. Clear guidelines on tool purpose and usage bring coherence and reduce fragmentation. Expanding the adoption of interactive platforms can also support more dynamic, collaborative knowledge exchange.
 5. **Diversify and enrich knowledge sharing methods:** Traditional high-impact practices such as workshops, mentoring and collaborative meetings should be continued and strengthened, while creative and innovative techniques should be used to stimulate fresh thinking and spark new ideas. Broadening the methodological toolkit helps engage different employee groups and encourages the sharing of both tacit and explicit knowledge. Organisations are encouraged to institutionalise innovation rituals, such as idea campaigns, hackathons or themed learning sessions, to embed experimentation and continuous learning into everyday work.
 6. **Implement incentive and recognition systems:** Knowledge sharing must be valued and rewarded. Both symbolic and financial incentives can reinforce positive behaviours and ensure that knowledge sharing activities are perceived as integral rather than optional. Recognition also plays an important role in countering fears that knowledge might be misused or that contributions will go unnoticed, thereby supporting a more open and collaborative culture.

The strategy document is available as full on the Annex 6.

4. Towards human capital excellence: conclusions and forthcoming actions

Various activities were implemented under Deliverable 3.5, 'Human Capital Excellence'. These included workshops, surveys, desk research, strategy documentation and the assessment of identified solutions. Regardless of their nature, the activities consistently reveal a dual principle of promoting human capital excellence and creating impact in young researchers. The first dimension of the dual principle is structural, technical, administrative and managerial, while the second one is human-centred and may include leadership and the creation of a culture of trust, for example. Seamlessly integrating these dimensions enables knowledge acquisition, construction and sharing, thereby fostering human capital excellence and positively impacting the development of research talent.

In order to fully harness the potential of research talents, it is essential to expand their knowledge and skills beyond their own sector and discipline. This expansion should encompass areas such as open science, GDPR issues, legislation, funding application preparation, and resource and time management. This is not only in line with the widening professional roles of researchers, but it may also contribute to employment opportunities and expand research beyond one's own discipline and national borders. This will increase the impact of research and develop human capital excellence, but also opens new avenues to talented researchers.

The findings of the activities conducted under Deliverable 3.5. also confirm the necessity of preparing the organisation, heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers for such dual structure, for instance, at the levels of organisational culture development, leadership and strategy. This finding confirms the work plan of the APPROACH project application where not only talents receive training, but also heads of units, administrators and other people in similar positions.

As forthcoming activities are still expected to organise a sixth meeting for heads of units and research groups, team leaders, and project managers in early December 2025, and an additional training on grant writing also in December 2025.

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6. Annexes

1. Annex I: The presentations of the workshops of Task 3.2 and Task 3.6

Presentation workshop 1

1

What is a good practice?

- A **good practice** can be defined as “anything that has been tried and shown to work in some way — whether fully or in part but with at least some evidence of effectiveness — and that may have implications for practice at any level elsewhere” (Serrat, 2008).
- A good practice can be e.g., methods, tools, techniques, models, and processes that has been shown to be effective in some context and might be effective in another too.

2

Today's Workshop

10:00–10:15 **Welcome and introduction to the workshop (15 min.)**
 Topic: *Managing multiple projects with limited resources. How to maintain consistent quality throughout: General Description and Overall Strategy. Tips to be discussed.*

10:15–11:15 **Topic of the workshop session (60 min.)**
 Miro Exercise related to internal communication:
 Individual reflection (10 min.)
 Group discussion (30 min.)
 Presenting and voting on the best practices (20 min.)

11:15-11:30 **Closing up and next steps (15 min.)**

3

Introduction

- Managing multiple research projects is complex due to limited funding, expertise, and infrastructure.
- Balancing **innovation, quality, and efficiency** is key.
- This presentation will provide some tips for best practices for prioritization, resource optimization, quality control, and team management.

4

The Challenge – Why Is This Important?

Many professionals manage multiple projects simultaneously with limited:

- Time – Deadlines overlap.
- Budget – Limited funding per project.
- People – Small teams or shared resources.

The risks:

- Declining quality due to stretched resources.
- Burnout among team members.
- Project delays and inefficiencies.

The key: Strategic planning, prioritization, and process optimization.

5

Prioritization Strategies – Focus on the Right Things

Assess Project Value: Not all projects are equal—some are high-impact, others can wait. Align projects with strategic objectives: Consider funding opportunities, societal impact, and technology readiness levels (TRLs).

Use **Impact vs. Feasibility Matrix** to prioritize efforts.

	Urgent	Not Urgent
Important	Do Tasks with clear deadlines and significant consequences if not completed in timely fashion.	Schedule Tasks without clear deadlines that will bring you closer to your long-term goals.
Not Important	Delegate Tasks that need to get done, but don't need your expertise in order to be completed.	Delete Tasks that distract you from your primary focus and don't add any measurable value.

6

Prioritization Strategies – Focus on the Right Things

Time Blocking & Scheduling: Allocate dedicated time slots for each project to avoid overlap and inefficiencies. Ensure resource allocation aligns with high-priority projects.

Agile & Iterative Approaches: Break down projects into manageable tasks and adapt dynamically to resource constraints. The agile iterative approach focuses on delivering value as fast as possible in increments, rather than all at once. Implement **Milestone-based decision gates** for go/no-go decisions.

7

Efficient Resource Allocation

- Optimize Human Resources:** Assign personnel based on skill sets, availability, and project demands. Use shared expertise across projects. Know the dynamics of your team.
- Leverage Automation:** Use digital tools for routine tasks to save time and increase productivity. Set up protocols where is possible. Knowledge sharing.
- Resource Sharing:** Utilize cross-functional teams and shared equipment to maximize efficiency.
- Outsource when necessary** – If internal resources are stretched, external help can be a cost-effective solution.
- Set Realistic Deadlines:** Avoid overcommitment by aligning project timelines with resource availability.

8

Maintaining Team Morale & Avoiding Burnout

Prevent burnout by setting realistic workloads and monitoring stress levels.

Celebrate small wins – Recognition boosts motivation.

Encourage learning – Teams that grow their skills are more engaged and productive.

Build flexibility into schedules – Avoid last-minute rushes.

WHAT ARE THE CAUSES OF EMPLOYEE BURNOUT?

- 1 Unmanageable workload
- 2 Toxic organizational culture
- 3 Toxic workplace behaviors
- 4 Micromanaging and managerial pressure
- 5 Poor workplace conditions
- 6 Boring, repetitive tasks
- 7 Lack of role clarity
- 8 Lack of compensation and recognition
- 9 External factors

Workshop Series 2025

9

Effective Communication

Set clear expectations – Define objectives, deliverables, and responsibilities upfront. Be consistent.

Use a centralized platform for tracking project progress (e.g., Notion, Trello, Monday.com).

Hold short, structured check-ins:

- Weekly stand-ups to track progress.
- Monthly reviews for strategic alignment.

Encourage transparent communication – Openly address issues before they escalate.

How to improve team communication

- 1 Resolve conflicts quickly
- 2 Encourage engagement
- 3 Promote bottom-up communication
- 4 Strive for transparency
- 5 Schedule one-on-one meetings
- 6 Provide consistent feedback

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10

Quality Assurance Methods

Standardized Workflows: Develop templates, checklists, and documentation to ensure consistency. Create SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) for recurring tasks—this ensures consistency. Use checklists to maintain uniformity across projects.

Regular Reviews & Feedback Loops: Implement progress reviews and peer evaluations to catch issues early. Define KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) and review work regularly.

Continuous Improvement: Use lessons learned from past projects to refine processes. Document best practices to speed up future projects.

Risk Management Planning: Identify potential risks early (e.g., resource shortages, technical challenges). Create mitigation strategies to maintain quality. Encourage a problem-solving culture – Team members should proactively suggest solutions.

Workshop Series 2025

13

Tools & Techniques - Leveraging Technology to Work Smarter

- Project Management Software:** OpenProject, Trello, Asana, Microsoft Project, Planner, or Jira for task tracking and collaboration.
- Version Control & Documentation:** Use Git, Confluence, or Notion to maintain project records and ensure traceability.
- Communication Platforms:** Slack, Microsoft Teams, or Zoom for real-time collaboration.
- Data Analytics & KPI Tracking:** Monitor performance using dashboards and key performance indicators (KPIs).

Workshop Series 2025

14

Conclusion & Key Takeaways

- Prioritize wisely** – Not everything is equally important.
- Optimize resources** – Allocate time, budget, and people strategically.
- Standardize for consistency** – Create templates, checklists, and procedures.
- Communicate effectively** – Keep all stakeholders informed and engaged.
- Stay adaptable** – Expect changes and plan for them.
- Use technology to your advantage** – Automate where possible.

Workshop Series 2025

Case Studies & Real-World Examples Exercise

- Research & Academia:** Strategies from successful EU-funded projects. Share insights from EU-funded projects (e.g., Horizon Europe consortia).
- Industry Best Practices:** Lessons from companies that optimize multi-project execution. Highlight successful multi-project research teams and their strategies.

Workshop Series 2025

Presentation workshop 2

APPROACH

ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

Struggling with team communication issues. How to prevent scheduling conflicts and delays.

24 June 2025

eu-project-approach.eu/

This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

OUTLINE

- Reasons of communication issues
- Examples (cases)
- Breakout discussions
- Prevention strategies
- Wrap-up & key takeaways

Good Practices Workshops Series

APPROACH

“What’s one word that describes your team communication lately?”

This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number: 101120397

3

Unclear or Misaligned Objectives and Scope

- ❑ **Vague Goals:** If the overall project goals are not clearly defined, specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART), different bodies will interpret them in their own way, leading to divergent paths and wasted effort.
- ❑ **Scope Creep:** Without a well-defined scope, additional tasks and features can be added without proper evaluation, leading to budget overruns, delays, and frustration as different parties perceive the “true” scope differently.
- ❑ **Conflicting Priorities:** Each partner often has its own internal priorities and agendas. If these aren't harmonized with the project's overarching objectives, departments might prioritize tasks that serve their individual goals over the collective project success.
- ❑ **Unmet Expectations:** When expectations about deliverables, timelines, and responsibilities are not clearly set and agreed upon by all parties from the outset, disappointment and conflict are inevitable.

4

Communication Breakdowns

- ❑ **Lack of a Communication Plan:** Without a clear strategy outlining who needs to communicate what, when, and how, information flow becomes haphazard, leading to missed updates, assumptions, and misinterpretations.
- ❑ **Ineffective Communication Channels:** Over-reliance on certain channels (e.g., email for urgent matters) or a lack of appropriate tools can hinder effective information exchange.
- ❑ **Information Overload/Underload:** Too much irrelevant information can bury critical details, while too little information leaves parties in the dark.
- ❑ **Poor Listening and Feedback Mechanisms:** If parties aren't actively listening to understand perspectives and there are no robust feedback loops, issues can fester and escalate.
- ❑ **Language Barriers:** In international or diverse teams, actual language differences or nuances in communication styles (e.g., direct vs. indirect communication) can lead to significant misunderstandings.

5

Unclear Roles, Responsibilities, and Authority

- ❑ **Ambiguity in Accountability:** When it's not clear who is responsible for what, tasks can be duplicated, overlooked, or fall into “gaps” between responsibilities, leading to blame and frustration.
- ❑ **Overlapping Responsibilities:** If two or more bodies believe they are responsible for the same task, it can lead to turf wars, inefficiencies, and resentment.
- ❑ **Lack of Defined Authority:** Without clear lines of authority for decision-making, progress can stall as parties wait for approvals or dispute who has the final say.
- ❑ **Siloed Working:** When bodies work in isolation without proper coordination or understanding of how their work impacts others, conflicts arise from a lack of integrated effort.

6

Cultural Differences (Organizational and National)

- ❑ **Varying Work Ethics and Norms:** Different organizations or cultures may have distinct approaches to deadlines, quality, hierarchy, and problem-solving, which can clash.
- ❑ **Communication Styles:** Some cultures prefer direct communication, while others favor indirect or high-context communication, leading to misinterpretations if not understood.
- ❑ **Decision-Making Processes:** Differences in how decisions are made (e.g., hierarchical vs. consensus-driven) can cause frustration and delays.
- ❑ **Attitudes Towards Conflict:** Some cultures may be more open to direct confrontation, while others prefer to avoid conflict, which can make resolution difficult.
- ❑ **Trust and Relationship Building:** In some cultures, building personal relationships is paramount before effective collaboration can occur.

7

Case 1: The Missed Update

A key team member finishes a crucial part of their work, which another team member is dependent on. Instead of updating the shared project management tool or notifying the dependent person directly, they assume the other person will “figure it out” or check on their own. The dependent team member then wastes time waiting or starts their part of the work based on outdated assumptions.

Communication Issue: Failure to provide timely updates, assuming others are aware of progress, lack of transparency.

Consequences: Project delays, missed opportunities, increased frustration, decreased productivity.

8

Case 1: Information Sharing

Implement a Centralized Knowledge Base
 What: Use a tool (e.g., Notion, Confluence, Guru) to store all project documentation, policies, meeting notes, and frequently asked questions in an easily searchable format.
 How it helps: Provides a single source of truth, reducing repeated questions and ensuring everyone has access to the latest information.

Regular Stand-up or Check-in Meetings:
 What: Regular Short meetings (especially effective for agile teams) where each member briefly shares what they worked on, what they plan to work on, and any blockers.
 How it helps: Fosters transparency, allows for quick identification of dependencies and potential roadblocks, and encourages proactive updates.

9

Case 1: Information Sharing

Cross-Functional Collaboration Tools:
 What: Utilize project management software (e.g., Asana, Trello, Jira) that allows teams to track tasks, assign owners, set deadlines, and see overall project progress.
 How it helps: Provides visibility across departments, helps break down silos by showing how different pieces of work fit together.

Scheduled Information Sharing Sessions:
 What: Dedicate specific meetings or recurring agenda items for different teams or individuals to share updates on their work, learnings, or challenges.
 How it helps: Ensures important information isn't missed and promotes a culture of shared knowledge.

10

Case 2: The Passive-Aggressive Feedback

A team member is consistently late with their deliverables, impacting the rest of the team. Instead of addressing the issue directly and constructively, their teammates make passive-aggressive comments in team chats or privately vent to other colleagues, creating a tense and uncomfortable atmosphere.

- Communication Issue:** Avoidance of direct feedback, fear of conflict, lack of established feedback mechanisms.
- Consequences:** Unresolved issues, decreased morale, resentment, breakdown of team cohesion.

Event's Name & Date

11

Case 2: Feedback & Conflict Resolution

Foster a Culture of Psychological Safety:
 What: Managers and team leaders should actively encourage open communication, make it safe to ask "dumb questions," admit mistakes, and voice concerns without fear of retribution.
 How it helps: Builds trust, encouraging direct and honest feedback, and making conflict resolution more constructive.

Establish Clear Feedback Mechanisms:
 What: Implement structured opportunities for peer feedback sessions. Provide training on how to give and receive constructive feedback.
 How it helps: Creates a safe space for addressing issues directly, prevents passive-aggressive behavior, and promotes growth.

Train in Conflict Resolution Techniques:
 What: Provide workshops or resources on active listening, empathy, non-violent communication, and negotiation skills.
 How it helps: Equips team members with the tools to address disagreements respectfully and find mutually agreeable solutions.

Event's Name & Date

12

Case 3: The Invisible Work Package

Scenario:
 In a Horizon Europe project with ten partners, one academic partner is tasked with developing an internal data validation tool. However, because their deliverables are not public-facing or directly connected to milestones, their work receives little attention in meetings. Other partners assume they're not making progress. The WP leader, feeling undervalued and excluded from major discussions, becomes disengaged and delivers late, triggering a domino effect on dependent tasks.

Communication Issue:
 Lack of visibility for supporting roles
 Unequal airtime in meetings
 Assumptions about progress

Event's Name & Date

13

Case 3: Strategy

Task Visibility Reviews: Include a short "progress radar" in every WP meeting where each team shares what they're working on—even non-critical tasks.

Rotating Meeting Chairs: Give every WP or task leader the opportunity to chair a meeting, which increases awareness and respect.

Peer Showcases: Allocate 10 minutes in monthly meetings to let quieter partners demo or explain their progress, reinforcing their value to the group.

Event's Name & Date

14

Making Communication Work for Your Team: Key Takeaways

- Keep it Clear**
 - Don't leave things to interpretation—say what you mean.
 - A shared plan for who communicates what, when, and how is your best defense against chaos.
- Make Work Visible**
 - If others don't see your progress, they might assume there isn't any.
 - Use short updates, visual boards, or demos to show what's happening—even behind the scenes.
- Choose the Right Tools for the Job**
 - Match the tool to the message: not everything needs an email.
 - Keep one place where everyone can find the latest info.
- Build Communication into the Culture**
 - Start meetings with check-ins, not just task lists.
 - Give space for feedback, questions, and clarifications.
 - Take turns leading meetings to hear different perspectives.
- Be Proactive, Not Reactive**
 - Set expectations early and revisit them often.
 - Don't wait for problems—check in on how communication is going.
 - Reflect together mid-way through a project, not just at the end.

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Event's Name & Date

15

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Presentation workshop 3

ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

Factors considers for an efficient filling system in your organization: Examples of timesheets

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1

OUTLINE

- Efficient Document Filing Systems
- Effective Timesheet Management
 - Practical tips, recommended tools, EU-specific requirements

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

2

Why Organized Filing is Critical for EU Projects

- Quick access to contracts, deliverables, invoices
- Audit readiness – prove implementation and costs
All participants must keep records and other supporting documentation to prove proper implementation and costs claimed
- Speeds up reporting and reduces errors when preparing financial or progress reports
- Supports collaboration and knowledge sharing among partners

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

Standardized Structure & Naming Conventions

- Define Logical folder hierarchy (Project > WP > Task > Date) – consistent across the consortium
- Use clear, consistent filenames (include project acronym/ID, WP number, date, version) – e.g. PROJ123_WP2_DataAnalysis_v1.0.docx
- Document your naming scheme (e.g. a one-page guideline) so all team members use the same format

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

Centralized Storage & Access Control

- Store documents in one central system (e.g. SharePoint/OneDrive, Google Drive, Nextcloud) accessible to all partners
- Assign appropriate permissions/roles (Coordinators have full edit, partners have access to their tasks)
- Use project management or DMS platforms with built-in filing (OpenProject, FP-Tools, eMDESK)
- Enable version control or maintain a changelog so past versions are recoverable

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

Metadata, Indexing & Search

- Tag key documents with metadata (project acronym, WP, year, keywords) in your DMS or even in filenames
- Take advantage of full-text search in modern platforms (e.g. SharePoint search, Nextcloud search) to find files fast
- Maintain a simple index (e.g. spreadsheet of major deliverables and where to find them) as a “master list”
- For research outputs, deposit data in repositories (Zenodo, OpenAIRE’s ARGOS) with DOIs; include links in your filing system

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

5

6

Security, Backup & GDPR

- Protect sensitive data: use encryption, strong passwords, and two-factor authentication on storage systems
- Ensure GDPR compliance: store personal data only when necessary and limit access (use secure platforms)
- Regularly back up the repository (both cloud versioning and offline copies) to prevent data loss
- Monitor access logs if available to track who viewed/edited important files

Meeting Administrators, managers and leaders team

Record Retention & Audit Readiness

- Save all supporting docs (timesheets, invoices, travel receipts, contracts, meeting minutes) labeled with project info
- EU rule of thumb: keep records at least 2 years after the final payment (often longer if National rules apply)
- Organize an “Audit Binder” or digital audit folder: a checklist of required docs and where they are stored
- After each reporting period, archive that period’s final files (e.g. /Archive/Year1/) to clean up active folders

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Section 2 – Efficient Timesheet Management

- Accurate effort reporting is essential for financial compliance and project monitoring
- Will cover EU-specific rules (e.g. Horizon Europe), best practices, and tool recommendations

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Why Accurate Timesheets Matter

- Personnel costs often make up a large part of EU project budgets
- Timesheets provide the basis for claiming staff effort and justifying the funds request
- Ensure transparency: auditors will verify that claimed days match actual work
- Helps project managers monitor effort vs. plan and adjust allocations

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9

10

EU Requirements for Timesheets

- Horizon Europe Art.20: must use “reliable time records” or monthly signed declarations (see EC template)
- Time records must be dated and signed at least monthly by the person and supervisor
- Minimum info: project acronym/ID, beneficiary name, year, person’s name, days worked, signatures
- If digital: system must allow electronic validation (login) and maintain an audit trail

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11

Daily Practices & Accuracy

- Daily Entries: Update the timesheet every day (or week) to avoid missing data
- Ensure all claimed time is actual work (don’t count weekends, sick or vacation days)
- Describe tasks/WP contributions clearly on the timesheet for traceability
- Managers should review and sign off on entries promptly each month

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12

Timesheet Tools & Automation

- Use a time-tracking tool (digital record = easier audits): e.g. eMDESK (tailored for Horizon EU)
- Free/Self-hosted options: Clockify, Toggl, Kimai, Odoo Timesheet – ensure export of logs for backup
- For PM platforms: consider Jira+Tempo plugin, OpenProject, or even dedicated ERP timesheets (Odoo Community)
- Enable automated reports: many tools can summarize hours by WP, highlight unapproved entries, and export to Excel/PDF

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13

Integrating Timesheets with Monitoring

- Link timesheet entries to project tasks/deliverables in your PM tool (e.g. Gantt chart, Jira issues)
- Use timesheet reports to update effort spent vs. baseline (dashboards or Excel pivots)
- Monitor budget burn: compare claimed person-days to planned person-months in each period
- Regularly review discrepancies (e.g. if much more/less time logged than planned, investigate)

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14

Summary & Resources

- Filing: Consistent folder structure and naming (reflect WP/task/date) save time; central, secure storage with backups is essential.
- Records: Keep all evidence (timesheets, receipts, deliverables) and retain for audits.
- Timesheets: Log effort daily, get monthly sign-off, use EC template or reliable software.
- Tools & Templates: Many free/EU-friendly tools exist (links below); always ensure they meet EC requirements (audit logs, signatures).
- Next Steps: Review your current system against these best practices; train team on any new tools or procedures.

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Presentation workshop 4

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APPROACH

APPROACH: Part 2 of the theme: APPROACH Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders, titled “Part Two – Struggling with Team Communication Issues: How to Prevent Scheduling Conflicts and Delays.”

Meeting online 1.9.2025

VAASA UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

1

Issues in communication: issue areas

1. PEOPLE-RELATED ISSUES
2. ORGANISATORY ISSUES
3. TECHNICAL and LEGAL ISSUES
4. OTHER ISSUES

APPROACH: Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders 1.9.2025

2

1. People-related issues: examples of issues

- Cultural issues.** National, regional, sectorial, occupational, language, etc.
- University versus SME in communication**
- Different levels of experience**
- Different hierarchies**
- Target group related issues.**
- Usability and user orientation**
- Trust and other people issues.**
- The lack of clarity of communication**
- Poor and delayed feedback from participants.** May confuse the process, or people already have other engagements
- Different workers,** including neurotypical people, physical conditions and disabilities.
- Participation for all**
- Other priorities**

APPROACH: Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders 1.9.2025

1. People-related issues: examples of solutions

A LIST OF POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

- The human being is the starting point
- Clear communication: simple, clear to the point, lists, highlight, emphasise, tables, colour code, etc. avoid long descriptive texts. Shorter emails
- Clarify the processes, timings and other issues at the beginning and repeat regularly
- Clear roles and responsibilities, materials and instructions. Lists of activities with key performance indicators, deadlines, roles, responsibilities, etc
- Team forming: a kick-off meetings, preferable face-to-face to form the team and establish communication. To make sure that everything is clear
- Create a trustworthy working atmosphere and create shares points and experiences between the team: let them get to know each other
- Target group understanding
- A backup system and people
- Plain language
- Support for new-comers
- Different timeslots if needed, organize meetings early
- Meetings: lots of meetings with partners, regular team meetings, e.g. team meetings. More internal meetings per task, work package.
- Meetings: lots of meetings with partners, regular team meetings, e.g. team meetings. More internal meetings per task, work package.
- Virtual meetings to support face-to-face meetings.
- Team forming and updating
- Communication, communication, communication, e.g. including regular bulleting.
- Working guide, e.g. management guide with deadlines
- Clarifying any work documents and making them easily usable
20. Examples, cause effect
- Good communication tools for all. Mobile and digital tools to support communication
- Collaborative platforms
- Reminders
- Discover, respect, and discuss before judging. The reason might be e.g. that email does not work
25. Examples

APPROACH: Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders 1.9.2025

1. People-related issues: cases

Case 1: University versus SME communication

Universities and research institutions tend to be more focused on details, doing everything by the book and in many cases relatively slower when it comes to developing a product/service. Contrary to that, companies focus mainly on monetizing the RND results faster and may (in some cases) hide some issues under the carpet. As far as the product is functional and delivers what it promises

Scientists' meetings also tend to be too long and more "philosophical" - in extreme cases out of topic. In my experience, scientists in their communications tend to be more elaborate and include more details. This is not always efficient in business

Solutions include: clear rules, communication deadlines and style, clear communication channels

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Case 2: Disappearing people

People in the project keep on disappearing, for example when have promised to deliver something. You have already provided clear timelines, working rule, roles and responsibilities, organise regular meetings, and send clear and regular project communications. In addition, you have agreed on the task together. What can you do? You may first make sure that people are receiving emails and communication. Your email might be in junk mail. It is worth to check this right at the beginning of the work process. You can call them.

See if any external things impact communication. Discuss with these parties and people what might be the issues. For example, you might be facing a neurodivergent person who easily becomes overwhelmed and needs time to recharge. Perhaps another mean of communication could help this person?

Have another person in the communication chain too. If the first person is not able to communicate, the other might receive the message.

5

2. Organisatory issues: examples and possible solutions

ISSUES

- Descriptions and instruction**
- Structures**
- Usability of things**
- The use of processes: new and existing**
- Unfollowed administration**

A LIST OF POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

- In addition to those in people dimension.
- Have clear instructions and descriptions that are easily available. Use infographics, matrices, etc. where useful. Add also where to ask help.
- Explain with examples and cause-effect paths.
- Make things usable: font, language, colours, etc.
- Reduce resistance positively.
- Help people make connection points between experiences and what they already know: use also analogies.
- Use change management.
- Inform about things on time.

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2. Organisatory issues: cases

Case 1: Introducing new practices

An organisation starts to use a new signature process. There change is drastic and there are plenty of things signatures are needed.

Therefore, the organisation informs about the issue early and organises an online training about it that will be recorded. There are a few different options for the event to cover as many employees as possible. In addition, employees have an opportunity to ask questions in advance.

It also invests in a transfer period and provides a new signature matrix with roles, the training video and an infographic with instructions of the process to all current and future workers. The heads of units function as contact people and provide assistance when needed.

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Case 2: Unfollowed administration

Administration is unfollowed by the contents and deadlines. Something needs to be done. The templates and materials have been tested with the participating people and initial instructions given. This has not helped though. Therefore:

- A separate meeting about issues is organized. For this meeting a list of any impacting issues is created.
- The meeting starts with the basic things, description and instructions. People are asked what is easy and what is complicated. These issues are discussed together: Is the issue usability? Or communication or something else? Other priorities?
- Examples of how and why to make something are told and shown, as well as cause effects. Moreover attitude changing exercises are provided (in case there are mental blockages).
- After this individual meeting and follow-up is organized to see that everything would be understood and people would get enough support.

7

3. Technical and legal issues: examples and possible solutions

ISSUES

- Access issues**
- Equipment issues**
- Usability issues**
- Different levels of mastering technology**
- Internet breaks etc.**
- Bodily functioning email**
- Cybersecurity.** Wrong communication policies may cause cybersecurity issues as well.
- GDPR**
- A variety of different tools.** In some cases there is no unified channel for communication across teams. Different tools are used. The flexibility to choose between online documents/spreadsheet editors (e.g. google docs) online collaborative platforms (jira, trello, MS Teams, asana etc.) or other tools may be nice but this heterogeneity may be unproductive in some cases.

A LIST OF POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

- Make sure that everyone has access to any tools, platforms, etc. and is able to use them. Provide support if needed.
- Make sure that every organization can use the selected systems and equipment.
- Take into account any human factors, e.g. disabilities, in the use of the systems and equipment.
- Use language that is common for all.
- Have a backup plan for breaks in internet and other systems.
- Make sure that the selected technical solutions respect GDPR.

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Other issues with team communication

- There might be any other issues creating scheduling conflicts and delays.
- 'Noise' often creates additional distractions scheduling conflicts and delays. It might be physical noise that, for instance, prevents form hearing important issues in a meeting, but it may also be external interruptions and other disturbance, or timing issues. In such case, use any external aids that may help overcoming them. This might be, for instance, quiet working times, notes, or showcasing to other people what is the overall work load for all.
- Use additionally examples from the previous issue areas to tackle scheduling conflicts and delays.

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A collective list of potential solutions

- The human being is the starting point
- Clear communication: simple, clear to the point, lists, highlight, emphasise, tables, colour code, etc. avoid long descriptive texts. Shorter emails
- Clarify the processes, timings and other issues at the beginning and repeat regularly
- Clear roles and responsibilities, materials and instructions. Lists of activities with key performance indicators, deadlines, roles, responsibilities, etc
- Team forming: a kick-off meetings, preferable face-to-face to form the team, agree on processes and rules, etc. to form the team and establish communication. To make sure that everything is clear
- Create a trustworthy working atmosphere and create shares points and experiences between the team: let them get to know each other
- Target group understanding
- A backup system and people
- Plain language
- Support for new-comers
- Different timeslots if needed, organize meetings early
- Meetings: lots of meetings with partners, regular team meetings, e.g. team meetings. More internal meetings per task, work package.
- Meetings: lots of meetings with partners, regular team meetings, e.g. team meetings. More internal meetings per task, work package.
- Virtual meetings to support face-to-face meetings.
- Team forming and updating
- Communication, communication, communication, e.g. including regular bulleting.
- Working guide, e.g. management guide with deadlines
- Clarifying any work documents and making them easily usable
20. Examples, cause effect
- Good communication tools for all. Mobile and digital tools to support communication
- Collaborative platforms
- Reminders
- Discover, respect, and discuss before judging. The reason might be e.g. that email does not work
25. Examples
- Have clear instructions and descriptions that are easily available. Use infographics, matrices, etc. where useful. Add also where to ask help.
- Explain with examples and cause-effect paths.
- Make things usable: font, language, colours, etc.
- Reduce resistance positively.
- Help people make connection points between experiences and what they already know: use also analogies.
- Use change management.
- Inform about things on time.
- Make sure that everyone has access to any tools, platforms, etc. and is able to use them. Provide support if needed.
- Make sure that every organization can use the selected systems and equipment.
- Take into account any human factors, e.g. disabilities, in the use of the systems and equipment.
- Use language that is common for all.
- Have a backup plan for breaks in internet and other systems.
- Make sure that the selected technical solutions respect GDPR.

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10

The next steps

- **The human being is the starting point**
- Structures
 - Making it usable
 - #ThatIsDead
- In case of new practices
 - **Linked to change management**
 - **Not only to inform verbally**
 - **Inform on time – early enough**
 - **Always written information and instructions: easy way easy to find**
 - **Define roles and new responsibilities and tell what it means**
 - **Easy and logical to find**
- In some cases there is no unified channel for communication across teams. Different tools are used. The flexibility to choose between online document/spreadsheet editors (e.g. google docs), online collaborative platforms (jira, trello, MS Teams, asana etc.) or other tools may be nice but this heterogeneity may be unproductive in some cases.
- Wrong communication policies may cause cybersecurity issues as well.
- **Cybersecurity**
- **GDPR to follow**

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11

Solutions - Strategies

- **Communication tools**
- **Collaboration platforms**
- **Shorter emails**
- **Change management**
- **Reminders**
- **More internal meetings per task, work package**
- **Face-to-face**
- **Clear roles and responsibilities, materials and instructions**
- **Target groups understanding**
- **Mobile and digital tools to support communication**
- **A backup system and people**

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Presentation workshop 5

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ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

5th APPROACH Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders

"Juggling Several Projects at Once: How to Stay Organized"

7th October 2025

This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

1

OUTLINE

- The reality of managing multiple projects
- Common challenges that create chaos
- Building structure and setting priorities
- Tools and communication systems that work
- Delegation, teamwork, and leadership rhythm
- Reflection: how to turn chaos into clarity
- Key takeaways

Good Practices Workshops Series

2

The Everyday Reality

Research and project work often means:

- Many projects running together
- Conflicting deadlines
- Too many emails and meetings
- Limited time for real thinking

This is how most project environments look: full, demanding, fast. We can't remove complexity, but we can manage it with structure and rhythm.

Good Practices Workshops Series

3

Common Challenges

These are the main obstacles to good organization.

- Constant task switching
- Trying to control every detail
- Working reactively instead of proactively

Our focus breaks when we switch tasks too often. We also lose time when we react instead of planning.

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4

What Organization Really Means

Organization means:

- Clarity in roles and priorities
- A predictable rhythm of work
- Simple systems that everyone understands

Organization isn't about control, it's about clarity. When teams have rhythm, work-flows and people feel calm.

Good Practices Workshops Series

5

The Importance of Structure

Clear structure brings:

- Better focus
- Smoother teamwork
- Fewer delays
- More time for creative thinking

"When people know where things are and what's expected, stress drops immediately. Structure makes collaboration easier for everyone."

Good Practices Workshops Series

6

Weekly Planning Habit

Weekly planning keeps projects steady:

- Review last week's progress
- Move incomplete tasks
- Choose 3 clear goals for next week

"This habit keeps chaos from building up. A short planning moment creates calm and direction for the whole team."

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7

Prioritizing What Matters

When everything feels urgent, ask:

- Is it really important?
- What has the biggest impact?
- What can wait or be delegated?

"Use these questions to manage attention. Sometimes the loudest task is not the most important one."

The Eisenhower Matrix

	Urgent	Not urgent
Important	Do it first High-value tasks that have set deadlines & consequences if not completed in time. Ex. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalizing materials for launch • Fixing an emergency technical problem • Handling a customer conflict 	Schedule it High-value tasks around long-term goals with no set deadline. Ex. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategizing your product roadmap • Taking a training course • Revamping your marketing strategy
Not important	Delegate it Low-value tasks that need to be completed, but don't require your expertise - busywork. Ex. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responding to some emails • Managing meetings • Scheduling your calendar 	Delete it Low-value tasks that interrupt your focus & pull time from your other tasks. Ex. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unproductive meetings • Inconsequential to-dos • Social media

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8

Simple Tools for Organization

Good tools are:

- Shared trackers (Google Sheets, Asana, Trello)
- Clear responsibilities and deadlines
- Regular updates from all partners

"Use one shared space where everyone can see progress. Even a simple shared spreadsheet can prevent confusion."

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9

Communication Discipline

To avoid confusion:

- One main channel per project
- End meetings with clear actions
- Store all decisions in one place

"Communication systems save time. If you agree on one main space for messages and decisions, your team gains hours every week."

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10

Delegation and Collaboration

Delegation works when:

- Goals are clear
- Tasks match skills
- Progress is reviewed regularly

"Delegation is not about control. It's about distributing work clearly so everyone knows their role."

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11

Managing Energy and Focus

Productivity depends on:

- Doing demanding work at high-energy times
- Grouping similar tasks
- Taking short breaks

"Managing energy is more effective than managing time. Know when you're most focused, and protect that time for deep work."

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12

Leadership and Team Rhythm

Leaders set the pace.

- Calm leadership = calm teams
- Predictability builds trust
- Clear rhythm reduces stress

"When leaders stay organized and calm, the team follows. Rhythm and stability help people perform better and feel supported."

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13

Reflection Exercise

Think about your current projects:

- What creates the most confusion or pressure?
- What simple change could improve it?

"Take a moment to reflect. What small step could make your week more organized, a checklist, a shared folder, a meeting rule? Small improvements have big effects."

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14

Closing

We will always have many projects.
Project life will always be full, but it doesn't have to feel chaotic!

But with structure, clear priorities, and calm communication, we can manage them with confidence and balance.

Thank you for your attention.

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APPROACH

APPROACH Workshop for Administrators, Managers, and Leaders, titled "Juggling Several Projects at Once: How to Stay Organised"

Meeting online 8. October 2025
VAASA UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

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1

When the background works, one can focus on the core activity

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Images: Microsoft PPT image bank

2

Juggling Several Projects: How to Stay Organised

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Organisational level

1. The main task is to provide a reliable and enabling framework and environment for activities
2. Staff: enough skilled and talented staff to run projects
3. Processes, tools and materials for managing and tackling projects
 - Project portfolio
 - Worktime, resource and expense follow up
 - Technical platforms to work and store materials
 - Process descriptions
 - Role descriptions
 - Signature matrices
 - Equipment
 - Licenses etc.
 - Flexible staff processes
 - Data management processes
 - Access to research databases, etc.
- Usability
- Flexibility

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5

Project level 1/2

1. Take care of the 'background' for each project
2. Each project with its code project code, account place and place to store its materials
3. A clear project plan for each
4. Regular checkups of materials and after the project, storing materials as one main version
5. Agree on common rules for each project, e.g. communication, regular meetings, material storing and sending
6. Create clarity: Management and other handbooks and instructions. Avoid long theoretical descriptions and repetition. Provide clear explanations, summarise the essentials and use tables to make them quick and easy to read and understand.
7. Team formation: low hierarchy, icebreakers, face-to-face meetings...
8. Regular meetings and knowing what everyone does. Also balance with other work and tasks
9. Make sure everyone knows what each project is about
10. Clearly indicate the time the team can use for the project and how it is divided between the team.
11. Backup persons

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Project level 2/2

12. Backup persons
13. What can you 'recycle'?
14. Organise the 'background' for flexible management
15. Use classification, coding and names in work and reporting documentation to ensure that everyone knows which files belong to which work package, activity or working version, etc. For example, organise files and folders by work packages, year-month-day formats, etc.
16. Be proactive. Have all the administrative, financial and content documentation ready as soon as possible after the activity has taken place.
17. Provide coordinators and auditors with a clear and intuitive audit trail. You may also include links to file locations.
18. Help future workers. Someone new may take over your work or audit it. Make sure you document everything carefully in good time.
19. Translations and explanations.
20. Take into account the different holidays, bank holidays and working times in the various partner countries, and inform of any issues in advance. Unexpected delays can completely disrupt other people's schedules.

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Individual level

1. Many same tools and practices as at the project level.
2. Time slot thinking and mark to your calendar
3. Balanced prioritising of tasks and projects
4. Follow- body rhythm in work tasks
5. What can you combine and/or recycle
6. Constructive learning
7. Structure
8. Use your 'SMART's (Specific, Measurable, Achievable (or Attainable), Relevant, and Time-bound)
9. Task and memory help
10. Colour coding...

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2. Annex 2: The presentations of the workshops in Prague March 2025

'Designing Scientific Project Frameworks That Win: Strategies for Horizon Europe applications' at the workshop in Prague, in March 2025, presented by Andrea Nogová.

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ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

DESIGNING SCIENTIFIC PROJECT FRAMEWORKS THAT WIN: STRATEGIES FOR HORIZON EUROPE APPLICATIONS

ANDREA NOGOVÁ

This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

Horizon Europe - 9th Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021 – 2027)

- Budget of €95.5 billion
- It tackles climate change (European Green Deal), helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth
- The programme facilitates intersectoral collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges.
- It supports creating and better dispersing of excellent knowledge and technologies.
- It creates jobs, fully engages the EU's talent pool, boosts economic growth, promotes industrial competitiveness and optimises investment impact within a strengthened European Research Area.
- Legal entities from the EU and associated countries can participate.

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Technology Readiness Levels

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Overview of Horizon Europe – Key Expectations

Pillar I	Pillar II	Pillar III
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excellence High risk – high gain Bottom-up topics Scientific peers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact Addressing societal challenges Top-Down Topics Multi-disciplinary panels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact Transfer to Market Bottom-up/Top-Down Topics Multi-disciplinary panels

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Why Framework Design Matters?

Evaluators are paid to evaluate your proposal, not to read it

- Good science poorly presented won't get funded => The scientific idea is not enough
- Structure is crucial => Evaluators assess clarity, feasibility, impact, and coherence
- Your project framework is your storytelling engine

You're not just sharing science — you're telling a story

Psychological effect: A clear, logical, and persuasive project framework gives reviewers the confidence that you can deliver promised outputs!

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Know Your Audience – Who Are the Evaluators?

- Independent experts selected by the European Commission
- Diverse backgrounds: academia, industry, public/private sectors

Evaluators are assigned based on expertise

BUT: Not always deeply specialized in your niche field

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MSCA PF – Evaluation: who reads the proposals

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Proposal structure – MSCA-PF

- Part A (electronically): General information about the Proposal including Abstract (max. 2 000 characters), Administrative data on participating organisations, Budget, Ethics issues table, Call specific questions
- Part B1 (PDF upload): Excellence (10 page limit), Impact (No section page limit, excess pages will automatically be disregarded), Implementation
- Part B2 (PDF upload): CV (indicative length: 5 pages), Capacities of the participating organisations, Ethical aspects, Letter of commitment

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Know Your Audience – Who Are the Evaluators?

WHAT DO THE EVALUATORS EVALUATE?

- There are given [evaluation criteria](#)
- See the EC video for [more details](#)

5 KEY QUESTIONS FOR THE EXCELLENCE PART:

- WHAT?
- WHY?
- HOW?
- WHY YOU?
- WHY NOW?

LET THE FUTURE TELL THE TRUTH, AND EVALUATE EACH ONE ACCORDING TO HIS WORK AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS. THE PRESENT IS THEIRS, THE FUTURE, FOR WHICH I HAVE REALLY WORKED IS MINE.

NIKOLA TESLA

EXCELEON LISTS

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Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA)

- Fund excellent research and innovation and equip researchers at all stages of their career with new knowledge and skills, through mobility across borders and exposure to different sectors and disciplines:

„spell” words to remember

- EXCELLENT RESEARCH
- CAREER DEVELOPMENT
- INTERNATIONALITY
- INTERDISCIPLINARITY
- INTERSECTORALITY

Expecto Petrolium Expressive Petrolium

- MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships grant scheme is an individual grant
- Focused on your own excellent research activities
- Boost your own career and future career perspectives
- Grant is not provided to establish your research team, but you are expected to establish one in the future
- Two-way transfer of knowledge between experienced researcher (ER) and host institution (HI)

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Know Your Audience – Who Are the Evaluators?

Imagine you are an evaluator with limited time and many proposals to evaluate

- How would you distribute your time?
- What would you do as first in each of the proposals?
- What would catch your attention?

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Straight to the point—make it quick

- Scientific Excellence - Clear novelty (State-of-the-Art to Challenges) & Objectives (SMART)
- Coherence - Logic between aims, methods, and outcomes
- Feasibility - Resources, timeline, risk management
- Impact - Scientific, societal, economic
- Implementation - Work packages, responsibilities, budget

- Use a visual to illustrate:
 - ✓ Objectives + Methods + Outputs + Outcomes + Impact
 - ✓ Work Packages (WPs) mapped to Objectives
 - ✓ Clear links between deliverables, milestones, risks, and dissemination

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Examples of visuals

Schematic representation of LipDel work packages with their communications.

Schematic representation of newly designed LYTAC molecule against intracellular or extracellular protein of interest.

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'How to design an appealing scientific project proposal' presented by Aristeides Bakandritsos

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ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

How to design an appealing scientific project proposal (part II)

Dr. Aristeidis Bakandritsos
CATRIN - Palacký University Olomouc
VSB - Technical University of Ostrava
a.bakandritsos@upol.cz

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OUTLINE

1. How to approach the proposal writing
2. How to compose a strong consortium
3. How to be convincing in terms of the KPIs

Speaker's Name & Date

Proposal writing

1. Be clear and understandable
2. Read many times and optimize structure, language, clarity
3. Hard work / time is needed – only top 8 % will receive funding

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‘Strategies For Researchers for Sustainable Success’ presented by Eirini Ioannou

ADVANCED PHOTONIC PROCESSES FOR NOVEL SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES

STRATEGIES FOR RESEARCHERS FOR SUSTAINABLE SUCCESS

EIRINI IOANNOU, PhD
Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials (RCPTM)
Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN)
Palacky University Olomouc

Certified Coach at Level 2 with the International Coaching Federation

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Aspects of Sustainable Success in Research:

Discussing strategies for sustainable success in research is crucial because research careers are highly demanding and long-term success isn't just about short-term achievements, it's about maintaining high-quality work, career satisfaction, and well-being over time.

Evidence* shows that researchers who focus on effective collaboration and communication, time management, goal setting and well-being are more likely to thrive in their careers.

We will focus on this workshop on strategies to help researchers stay adaptable and resilient in a rapidly changing environment and address common challenges such as high pressure and professional – personal life balance.

*Van den Pout, L.J.J., Daal, O.C. Promoting the Emergence of Team Flow in Organizations. Int J Appl Bus Res 7: 148-159 (2022)
van der Horst, M., Groenewald, S. & Kopers, B. Goal Setting in Teams: Goal Clarity and Team Performance in the Public Sector. Review of Public Personnel Administration, 38(4), 473-493 (2018)

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OUTLINE

Part I: Working and Collaborating effectively

- Joint Vision & Clear Goals – Aligning personal and team objectives (more explicitly in part II)
- Defined Roles & Responsibilities – Improving efficiency
- Building Trust & Psychological Safety – Encouraging open dialogue and knowledge sharing
- Effective Communication: Principles of clear and constructive communication
Active listening and feedback for collaboration

Part II: Goal Setting & Time Management

1. The Power of Goal Setting
 - The importance of defining clear research and career goals
 - SMART goals adapted for researchers
2. Strategies for Time Management & Productivity
 - Time management techniques
 - Balancing research and personal life
 - Sustainable work habits

Career Days: Connecting Research Talents with Business Opportunities, 27th of March 2025

Part I: Working and collaborating effectively

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Joint Vision & Clear Goals

A shared vision ensures that all team members align their efforts toward common research objectives.

Why It's Important:

- Increases motivation and engagement*
- Reduces misalignment in research priorities
- Strengthens long-term research impact and funding potential.

How to Achieve It:

- Co-create the vision: Discuss team research focus and expected outcomes.
- Break down goals: Set SMART goals (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound).
- Regular check-ins: Adapt the vision based on progress, challenges, or new opportunities.

*Locke, E. & Latham, G., Building a Practically Useful Theory of Goal Setting and Task Motivation: A 35-Year Odyssey. Annu. Rev. Psychol. 57, 705-732 (2006)

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Defined roles and responsibilities

Clear roles help avoid duplication of efforts, inefficiency and misunderstandings

Why It's Important:

- Reduces frustration from overlapping or unclear responsibilities
- Improves accountability and productivity
- Helps team members play to their strengths (DISC assessment)

How to Achieve It:

- Clarify expertise areas: Who is responsible for what?
- Use a RACI framework: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed to define roles.
- Be flexible: Adjust responsibilities based on project needs.

*Cobb A. & Padmanabhan, L., Leading Teams: Setting the Stage for Great Performance, Administrative Science Quarterly, 46, 712 (2001)

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Building Trust and Psychological safety

Psychological safety means team members feel comfortable expressing ideas, asking questions, and admitting mistakes.

Why It's Important:

- Leads to better problem-solving and innovation*
- Encourages open dialogue and knowledge sharing
- Reduces fear of failure, improving collaboration and creativity

How to Achieve It:

- Lead by example: Encourage constructive feedback and open communication.
- Foster inclusion: Ensure all voices are heard and respected in discussions.

Brisson, Amy (2011) Psychological Safety, Trust, and Learning in Organizations: A Group-level Lens. Trust and Distrust in Organizations: Dilemma and Approaches

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Our Brain and Threat

Avoidance (THREAT) vs **Approach** (REWARD)

- Avoidance (THREAT):** Emotionally Driven, Disengaged, Problem Focused, Disconnected
- Approach (REWARD):** Logically Driven, Engagement, Solution Focused, Connected

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SCARF Model

Dr. David Rock, 2008

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The SCARF model

This memorable framework from Dr. David Rock helps communicators recall the five key domains of psychological safety. When these pillars may be threatened, we should anticipate an instinctively avoidant response - and look for ways to soften the impact.

Threatened by...	Replenished by...
Status Embarrassment, feeling singled out, pointed at or surprising feedback, competence being questioned	Mutual respect, separating the work from the person, public acknowledgment, job security
Certainty Constantly shifting plans, unseen forces at work, unclear goals, major "leave unknown", fuzzy strategy	Clear strategies, timelines and deliverables, steady expectations, sense of the bigger picture
Autonomy Micromanaging, pressure over outcome, "only one right way to do it", questions & challenge unwelcome	Empowered teams, collaborative decision-making, flexibility in acceptable approaches, playing to unique strengths
Relatedness Impersonal demands, faceless bureaucracy, "computer says no", disconnected leadership	Genuine human connections, putting a face to the task, doing things for and with others, team culture
Fairness Arbitrary application of standards, capricious rule changes, ignoring an agreement, unjust rewards	Rules that make sense, giving and taking, transparency, and consistent treatment for everyone

<https://www.bhmliterature.com/resources/scarf-model-david-rock-extended>

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Key parameters of Effective Communication

- 1. Clarity & Precision**
 - Structure communication (e.g., concise emails, structured meeting agendas)
- 2. Active Listening**
 - Foster an environment where all members feel heard and valued
 - Listen carefully, respond and reflect on what is being said
 - Be open to diverse perspectives
- 3. Constructive Feedback**
 - Use evidence-based feedback models like SBI (Situation-Behavior-Impact)
 - Encourage a culture of regular feedback, both upward and peer-to-peer
 - Balance critical and positive feedback to promote growth

Communication Channels & Adaptability

- Choose the right medium:
 - Email: Best for formal documentation
 - Meetings: Best for discussions and decision-making
 - Instant messaging/tools (for ex. Teams): For quick updates
- Be adaptable in communication styles based on the team and cultural context.

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Part II: Goal setting and Time Management

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What is Time Management

The coordination of tasks and activities to maximize the effectiveness of our efforts when working for certain goals

Why is it important for researchers?

Because of the nature of the work, which involves long-term projects, complex tasks and the need to balance multiple responsibilities

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Main aspects of Time management

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S.M.A.R.T. Goal Setting Method

S	SPECIFIC	
M	MEASURABLE	
A	ACHIEVABLE	
R	RELEVANT	
T	TIME BOUND	

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Example of a goal using SMART GOAL settings:

S	SPECIFIC	Finish 1 article in specific topic
M	MEASURABLE	1 article
A	ACHIEVABLE	Dedicating 1h/per day
R	RELEVANT	In an area of my research interest
T	TIME BOUND	by the end of the next 3 months

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BUILDING ON SMART GOAL SETTING

FROM GOAL SETTING — PLAN

- Clarifying the goal and focus
- Breaking down the end goal to smaller actionable steps
- Mapping out the time and resources needed for the goal
- Identifying the smallest action to take every day towards the goal
- Adding joy to the procedure, celebrating end goal

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Prioritizing

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#

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Creating clarity

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#
Collect experimental data for specific experiment				
Search the literature on specific topic				
Do a specific experiment				
Analyze scientific results				
Discuss results with a team member				
Prepare a scientific report				
Prepare for a group meeting presentation				
Prepare for submitting a scientific paper				
Attend a conference				

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 *Dr. Karli Novik, Compassionate calendar course, Body Brain Alliance

Creating clarity

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#
Collect experimental data for specific experiment	14/04/2025			
Search the literature on specific topic	22/04/2025			
Do a specific experiment	23/04/2025			
Analyze scientific results	28/04/2025			
Discuss results with a team member	02/05/2025			
Prepare a scientific report	11/05/2025			
Prepare for a group meeting presentation	15/05/2025			
Prepare for submitting a scientific paper	28/05/2025			
Attend a conference	02/06/2025			

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Considering emotions

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#
Collect experimental data for specific experiment	14/04/2025			
Search the literature on specific topic	22/04/2025			
Do a specific experiment	23/04/2025			
Analyze scientific results	28/04/2025			
Discuss results with a team member	02/05/2025			
Prepare a scientific report	11/05/2025			
Prepare for a group meeting presentation	15/05/2025			
Prepare for submitting a scientific paper	28/05/2025			
Attend a conference	02/06/2025			

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Considering others

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#
Collect experimental data for specific experiment	14/04/2025			
Search the literature on specific topic	22/04/2025			
Do a specific experiment	23/04/2025			
Analyze scientific results	28/04/2025		✓	
Discuss results with a team member	02/05/2025			
Prepare a scientific report	11/05/2025		✓	
Prepare for a group meeting presentation	15/05/2025			
Prepare for submitting a scientific paper	28/05/2025		✓	
Attend a conference	02/06/2025			

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Ready to start scheduling

Task	Deadline	Emotion	Others	#
Collect experimental data for specific experiment	14/04/2025			3
Search the literature on specific topic	22/04/2025			4
Do a specific experiment	23/04/2025		✓	5
Analyze scientific results	28/04/2025		✓	6
Discuss results with a team member	02/05/2025			8
Prepare a scientific report	11/05/2025		✓	7
Prepare for a group meeting presentation	15/05/2025			1
Prepare for submitting a scientific paper	28/05/2025		✓	2
Attend a conference	02/06/2025			9

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Scheduling and tasks

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Scheduling and managing tasks

- Create a schedule for daily and weekly activities, based on priorities
- Time Blocking: Allocating specific time slots for different tasks or activities to ensure focused work periods
- To do-lists
- Time-tracking
- Flexibility: Allow some free time to adjust plans as needed
- Digital tools: Trello, Asana, Google Calendar to organize plan and track tasks and time
- Analog tools: Journals and Planners (lead to increased commitment)

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Example of Time-Blocking using Google Calendar

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<https://bit.ly/1productivitymethod/time-blocking>

Managing distractions

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Procrastination

- Term for doing other actions - not the one we need to complete.
- Avoiding difficult emotions for difficult tasks
- Lack of clarity for a task

- Solution starts with awareness:
- Do I have all the information to complete certain task?
 - What do I need to know
 - How can I break the task to smaller pieces?
 - Explore how we feel about the task
- AND: Emotionally manage our feelings around the task

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Reflection

1. Data
• What are the data that I have about my week?

2. Analysis
• Was I clear on my priorities last week?
• How do I feel about my planning?
• Did I break down my goals to smaller tasks?
• What adjustments do I need to make?

3. Plan – leads to progress

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APPROACH

THANK YOU

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This project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

3. Annex 3: Presentation 'Unlock The Power of Your Data'

The presentation 'Unlock The Power of your Data' by Information Management Officer Bilal Naffaa from IMEC.

Agenda

- Open Science
- Data Management Plan
- Introduction to Data
- Metadata: Data About Data
- Data Storage: Zenodo

Open Science (OS)

- "As Open as Possible, as closed as necessary"
- Open Science is a legal obligation under Horizon Europe, Flemish funder FWO, VLAIO and other Funding agencies
- Research Data are freely available to:
 - Reuse
 - Redistribute
 - Reproduce

Data Management Plan

Data Management Plan Definition

A Data Management Plan, or DMP, is a document in which the researcher should outline how data will be handled throughout and after a project.

- What is in a DMP?**
 - Basic info
 - Description of data
 - Division of responsibilities
 - Resource allocation

Why are Data management plans everywhere?

Introducing Open Science (EU Commission)

- Open Science (OS) policy strives to quickly spread knowledge
- Requires: beneficiaries of research + innovation funding (you) to make research outputs available:
 - Publications in open access
 - Data as open as possible and as closed as necessary

← Data needs to be managed
You need to have a plan
"Data Management Plan"

2 reasons to make a DMP

Funders require them, but they are good for you too ...

- They help you keep track of **legal and security** issues.
 - Intellectual Property Rights?
 - Contractual agreements?
 - Confidential data?
 - Dual-use potential?
- They help you keep track of **your data**.
 - Where to store?
 - Should you store?
 - Where was that file again?
 - Is everyone working on the same version?

DMPs document how you handle your data

Send us your initial DMP (within the first 6 months of the project)

Send us your final DMP (Alongside the final report of the project)

What is Data ?

- Primary
- Secondary
- Tabular
- Nominal
- Observational
- Experimental
- Qualitative
- Quantitative
- Audio-visual
- Imagery

- General Definition: Any piece of information that conveys details about states or events.

- Funding agencies: Anything that contains information.

Into the Data: Metadata

Data About Data

- Metadata are crucial for making your data FAIR. They should be added continuously throughout your project, not just at the start or end. From a FAIR perspective, metadata are more important than the data itself, as they are always openly available and link research data and publications on the Internet of FAIR Data.
- Metadata is the interface that provides better descriptions for improved discovery of archives and special collections.¹
- The effect of metadata on end-users may be reflected in exclusive data, like the 90% boost in discoverability achieved through investment in semantic technology.²

¹ Schaffner, J. & OCLC Research. (2019). The Metadata in the Invisible Basin: Challenges for Better Discovery of Archives and Special Collections. *Open Access User Studies: OCLC Research*. <https://www.oclc.org/research/articles/news/articles/oclc-research-2019-24.pdf>

² Cornell, L. Y. (2014, September 26). The Experience of Good Metadata Linking enables us research success. *The Scholarly Kitchen: The Scholarly Kitchen*. <https://scholarlykitchen.socnet.umich.edu/2014/09/26/the-experience-of-good-metadata-linking-enables-us-research-success/>

Importance for Researchers and Science

- How can researchers and science benefit from metadata?

Researchers	Science
More Visibility and Citation	Facilitates data finding and reuse
Opportunities for collaborations	Enables new research and insights into the data.
Career recognition	Valuable data is protected
Decrease of non-compliance risks (legal, ethical, institutional and funders' policies).	Supports research integrity and reproducibility.

Where is the Metadata located within imec ?

- Describe
- Describe (data catalog) serves as a centralized database that stores and manages metadata within imec
- How to Use DataCatalog: The imec Catalog

Are you a project lead for a publicly funded project? If so, you need to upload your metadata to describe

> Please keep the following important remarks in mind:

- It is mandatory to upload your metadata as part of applying open science principles, ensuring it is sent to the publicly funded agencies especially at the end of the project.
- If you have a valid dataset during the project, please ensure its metadata is uploaded.
- It is recommended to upload at least one metadata for the project.
- Keep your metadata up to date. For example, if you change the name of the project or if a new colleague joins the project, etc..

What is Zenodo ?

Definition

- Zenodo is a general-purpose research repository designed to facilitate the sharing, preservation, and dissemination of research outputs across all scientific disciplines. Launched in 2013 by the CERN, Zenodo offers researchers and institutions a user-friendly space to deposit and archive various types of scholarly content, including datasets, software, presentations, publications, and more.

Searching for our community

Where should you go?

Upload your information assets

Uploading your assets (basic information)

Uploading your assets (basic information)

Basic information

Uploading your assets (recommended information)

Recommended information

Uploading your assets (recommended information)

Uploading your assets (funding, IDs, related works, references, software)

Uploading an asset (publications)

Uploading an asset (conference papers)

4. Annex 4: Presentation 'Open Science and Open Data'

'Open Science and Open Data' on Wednesday, 29 October 2025 by Jakub Navařík.

OPEN SCIENCE

RISKS

- 1) Data mining (open data)
- 2) High costs (open access)

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

F.A.I.R. Principles

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Findable data

Laboratory level

- Proper sample identification (unique code, central laboratory evidence, ...)
- All raw data must be accompanied with some kind of metadata (assignability to the sample)
- All measurements must be registered in a laboratory book (hardcopy or electronic)
- A responsible person must be designated

Publication level

- All published data must be safely stored to ensure their full availability during the publication lifetime
- All data must be assignable to individual images, graphs, etc
- A responsible person must be designated (typically corresponding author)

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Accessible data

Laboratory level

- Raw data and metadata are available for scientists who are working with them

Publication level

- All published data must be available for broad public
 - Previously on the request upon the containing author's team (typically corresponding author responsibility)
 - New trend is the unlimited public access through online repository

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Interoperable data

Laboratory level

- Typically no interoperability request
- Raw data are often processed by specialized software

Publication level

- All published data should be usable with standard software tools and standard PC
 - Using of standard open formats, like: *.TXT (ASCII), *.DOC, *.XLS, *.HTML, *.JPG, ...
 - Only exception is if there is no such possibility, then the data could be in method specific format

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Reusable data

Laboratory level

- Raw data are always reusable from their principle

Publication level

- All published data must be in a format and form which allows their reuse and evaluation by anyone

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařík

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

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OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
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OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
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 Interoperable
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OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
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Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
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 Interoperable
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Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

Findable
 Accessible
 Interoperable
 Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

- ✓ Findable
- ✓ Accessible
- ✓ Interoperable
- ✓ Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

OPEN DATA

Reusable data example

F.A.I.R

- ✓ Findable
- ✓ Accessible
- ✓ Interoperable
- ✓ Reusable

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

(META)DATA

Data behind data

- Data contains experimental results
- Metadata contains information about data:
 - Sample name and description
 - Measurement conditions
 - Instrument information
 - Operator information
 - Other information
- Included in data file or separated
- **Important for reproducibility!**

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

LABORATORY LEVEL

Data Management Plan

- Written set of rules and principles
- Determines how data is handled
 - Data formats
 - Data storage, sharing and backup rules
 - Metadata contents and formats
 - Responsible person
- Data loss prevention
- Easy onboarding of new employees
- Everyone knows exactly their duties

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

PUBLICATION LEVEL

Funding and Good practice

- **Typically defined by project funder**
- Good practice - open access cloud
 - Data are publicly available
 - F.A.I.R. principles are fulfilled
 - Free of charge service
- Requires to set rules on a team level
 - Project/Team Data management plan
 - Responsible person
- **Unacceptable to restrict access to data**
(data upon request, data upon REASONABLE request)

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

PUBLIC DATA REPOSITORY

Simple and effective

YOUR F.A.I.R Responsibility

- Interoperability
- Reusability

REPOSITORY F.A.I.R Responsibility

- Findability
- Accessibility

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

PUBLIC DATA REPOSITORY

How to do it?

- Register on Zenodo.org or similar
 - Zenodo is reliable public accessible scientific data repository running under the CERN facility
 - Registration can be done on <http://zenodo.org> (simple email registration & verification)
 - Any standard online repository which can fulfill FAIR requirements is suitable, not just Zenodo
- Prepare all the published data
 - The data must meet the requirements on **interoperability and reusability!**
 - Use open formats usable with any computer!
(if your instrument is using closed format, export data to open format and then upload both)
 - If you are uploading graph, do not forget to add the datasets for it, etc.!

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

PUBLIC DATA REPOSITORY

Practical example

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

Q&A

Open Science and Open Data | Jakub Navařik

Thank you

Jakub Navařik
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The Approach project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397
The Accelerator project receives funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101067318

5. Annex 5: Tas 3.4. Report on Open Science and Data Management Training Needs

As an annexed PDF

6. Annex 6: Knowledge Sharing-Interactive Employee Process, Strategy document

As an annexed PDF

APPROACH

Advanced Photonic PRocesses for novel sOlar energy hArvesting
teCHnologies

Survey report

Task3.4 Report on Open Science and Data Management
Training Needs (Survey Report)

Deliverable Lead: VAMK

Deliverable due date: 31 November 2025

This project receives funding in the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

Document Control Page	
Title	Report on Training Needs in Open Science and Data Management (survey report)
Creator	VAMK
Description	Report on Training Needs in Open Science and Data Management (survey report)
Creation date	31 November 2025
Type	Report
Language	English
Audience	<input type="checkbox"/> public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> confidential
Review status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> WP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by Partners <input type="checkbox"/> for approval by the WP leader <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for approval by the Project Coordinator

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Appendixes

Appendix 1. Survey Template

DISCLAIMER

The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the APPROACH project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.

Introduction

This document constitutes the report of the survey conducted as part of **Work Package 3** of the **APPROACH** project. The APPROACH project aims to promote open innovation, training, and cross-sectoral cooperation in solar energy harvesting (APPROACH Consortium, 2023). The objective of the survey was to identify and benchmark the experiences, preferences, and situations related to **open science and data management** among various stakeholder groups, including scientists, SME representatives, academics, policymakers, the general public, and other relevant actors from diverse sectors. The insights gathered through this survey are instrumental in supporting the planning and design of targeted training activities on **open science**, which is defined as a framework promoting transparency and collaboration (European Commission, 2016), **and data management**, that involves the processes of storing, organizing, and maintaining research data (OECD, 2017), with a particular focus on their application in **solar energy harvesting technology research**. Open science

The objectives of **Work Package 3** are to promote continuous learning, engagement, talent development, and capacity building among researchers and innovators, with the overarching goal of enhancing organizational performance, productivity, and overall effectiveness. In addition, WP3 aims to establish a comprehensive framework that serves as a practical guide for organizations to adapt, refine, and integrate their learning and development functions in alignment with their specific needs, priorities, and strategic objectives.

The present report is organized into five chapters. Following this introduction, **Chapter 1** outlines the **methodology** employed in the design, distribution, and data collection of the Open Science and Data Management Survey. **Chapter 2** describes the **structure and content** of the survey questionnaire, detailing the thematic areas and question design. **Chapter 3** presents the **findings and analysis** of the survey results, identifying key patterns, trends, and stakeholder perspectives. **Chapter 4** summarizes the **main findings and recommendations**, providing strategic directions for future training activities and workshops under the APPROACH project. Finally, **Chapter 5** offers the **conclusion and final remarks**, reflecting on the implications of the results for advancing open science and data management practices across participating countries and institutions.

This report represents one of the core deliverables under Work Package 3, providing essential input for the development of effective and responsive training programs on open science and data management.

I Data collection

The survey was conducted as part of Work Package 3 of the APPROACH project, with the objective of identifying and benchmarking experiences, preferences, and practices related to open science and data management among key stakeholder groups across participating countries. The survey was administered online using the Webropol platform through a structured questionnaire designed to collect both quantitative and qualitative data.

At the beginning of the questionnaire, all participants were presented with an informed consent statement explaining the purpose of the study, data confidentiality, and the voluntary nature of participation. Only those who provided their consent proceeded to complete the survey.

A total of 175 participants completed the questionnaire. Respondents represented a wide range of stakeholder groups, including scientists, SME representatives, policy makers, members of the general public, and other professionals engaged in research, education, and innovation-related activities. The survey was open to participants from six countries involved in the APPROACH network: Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, Greece, Ukraine, and Switzerland.

The distribution of participants by country was as follows:

Belgium: 19%

Czech Republic: 19%

Finland: 19%

Greece: 18%

Ukraine: 20%

Switzerland: 3%

The stakeholder composition of the survey respondents was as follows:

Scientists: 118 participants (67%)

SME representatives: 13 participants (7%)

Policy maker: 1 participant (1%)

General public: 22 participants (13%)

Others: 28 participants (16%)

The category “Others” encompassed respondents with a wide range of professional backgrounds, including QA engineers, quality control engineers, software developers, students, PhD candidates, engineers, lecturers, teachers, higher education leadership, business developers, HR professionals, project managers, project assistants, and corporate representatives, among others. This diversity of professional perspectives provided valuable insights into the experiences, perceptions, and training needs related to open science and data management, particularly in the context of solar energy harvesting research.

2 Structure of the Survey

The survey questionnaire was developed to collect information on participants' experiences, awareness, and practices related to **open science** and **data management**. It consisted of a series of closed and open-ended questions designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data. The questions were grouped into four thematic areas, as described below.

1. Background Information

This section gathered general information about the participants to enable analysis by professional and geographical background. Respondents were asked:

- Their **professional background**
- Their **primary country of residence or work**

2. Awareness and Experience with Open Science and Data Management

The second section examined participants' prior knowledge and practical experience with open science and data management. It included questions on:

- Awareness of the **concept of open science**
- Previous participation in **data management or open science training**
- Level of **involvement with scientific data**
- Main **challenges** faced in adopting open science and data management practices
- Perceived **benefits** of implementing open science
- Sectors that could **benefit most** from improved data sharing and open science
- **Privacy or legal concerns** that may hinder data sharing
- Factors that would **encourage broader adoption** of open science practices
- Awareness of **EU or national policies** supporting open science and data sharing

3. Current Practices and Compliance

This section focused on respondents' current approaches to data handling, sharing, and security. The questions covered:

- Use of **data management tools or repositories** (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub)
- Familiarity with or use of the **FAIR data principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

- Measures taken to ensure **data security and compliance** (e.g., GDPR)
- Willingness to **test new tools, platforms, or practices** for data management and open science
- Methods of **collaboration and data sharing** within teams or with external partners

4. Training Needs and Participation Preferences

The final section addressed respondents' perspectives on training in open science and data management. It included questions on:

- **Topics of interest** for future training activities
- **Preferred formats** for training or workshops (e.g., online, in-person, hybrid)
- **Barriers** to participating in such training
- Interest in **contributing further** to the development, testing, or evaluation of open science and data management tools or training within European initiatives such as the APPROACH project

The complete set of survey questions is provided in **Appendices 2–4**. The structure of the questionnaire allowed for the systematic collection of information from various stakeholder groups to support the objectives of **Work Package 3** and inform future training design within the APPROACH project.

3 Findings from the questionnaire

3.1 Awareness and Understanding of Open Science

Foster and Deardorff (2017) describe the Open Science Framework (OSF) as a tool that promotes open, centralized workflows by enabling capture of different aspects and products of the research lifecycle, including developing research idea, designing a study, storing and analyzing collected data, and writing and publishing reports or papers. This section presents the findings related to respondents' awareness, familiarity, and understanding of open science and data management principles. It examines the extent to which participants are acquainted with the concept of open science, their previous participation in relevant training activities, and their level of involvement with scientific data. Furthermore, it explores their knowledge and application of the FAIR data principles, awareness of data management tools and repositories, and familiarity with EU and national policies that support open science practices. The section concludes with reflections on the overall level of awareness and understanding among respondents, providing context for the subsequent analysis of current practices and training needs.

3.1.1 Awareness of the Concept of Open Science

The majority of respondents demonstrated a general awareness of the concept of open science. A total of 71.8% indicated that they had heard of open science, while 17.8% had not, and 10.4% were unsure. These results show that while awareness of open science is relatively widespread among participants, a considerable portion of respondents remain unfamiliar with the concept or uncertain about its scope and meaning.

3.1.2 Previous Participation in Open Science or Data Management Training

In terms of practical exposure, 45.1% of respondents reported having previously participated in open science or data management training, whereas 54.9% had not. This indicates that while nearly half of the participants have engaged in structured learning related to open science, the majority have not yet had formal training opportunities in this field.

3.1.3 Level of Involvement with Scientific Data

The level of involvement with scientific data varied across respondents. 48.0% reported daily engagement with data, 26.9% indicated occasional involvement, 17.1% were rarely involved, and 8.0% reported no engagement at all. These findings suggest that a significant proportion of respondents work directly with data on a regular basis, while others have limited or indirect interaction depending on their professional roles.

3.1.4 Familiarity with FAIR Data Principles

According to Wilkinson et al. (2016), the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) provide guidelines for improving the management and reuse of scientific data. Awareness of the FAIR data principles was uneven. 21.7% of respondents stated that they actively apply the FAIR principles in their work, and 29.7% were aware of them but not applying them. 14.3% had heard of the principles but did not fully understand them, 28.0% were unfamiliar with them, and 6.3% indicated that these principles were not applicable to their work. This variation highlights different levels of understanding and implementation across the respondent group.

3.1.5 Awareness of Data Management Tools and Repositories

A data repository is a secure platform for storing and sharing research data, such as Zenodo or GitHub (Pampel & Dallmeier-Tiessen, 2014). Regarding the use of data management tools and repositories, 40.6% of respondents reported using platforms such as Zenodo, GitHub, or other repositories for data storage and sharing, while 59.4% did not use any dedicated tools. This indicates that more than half of the respondents currently lack active engagement with established data management systems.

3.1.6 Awareness of EU and National Policies Supporting Open Science

Knowledge of existing policy frameworks related to open science and data sharing was relatively low among participants. Only 20.0% of respondents reported being aware of EU or national policies supporting open science, while 30.9% were unaware of such policies, and 49.1% were unsure. This reflects a limited understanding of the policy environment that underpins open science initiatives.

3.1.7 Reflections on Awareness and Understanding of Open Science

Overall, the survey results indicate that awareness of open science as a concept is relatively high among respondents, yet familiarity with its practical implementation, related principles, tools, and policy frameworks remains inconsistent. While many respondents are regularly involved in working with scientific data, fewer have received formal training or are aware of the frameworks and instruments necessary for effective data management. These findings point to the need for targeted awareness-raising and capacity-building initiatives to strengthen understanding and adoption of open science practices across different professional groups.

3.2 Current Practices in Data Management

This section provides an overview of how respondents currently manage, protect, and share research data within their professional or institutional settings. It explores existing approaches to **data security and compliance**, including adherence to GDPR, and examines the extent and nature of **collaboration and data sharing practices**. The section also assesses respondents' **willingness to test new tools and platforms** designed to enhance open science implementation. Together, these findings provide insight into the current state of data management practices and the degree of institutional preparedness for broader open science adoption.

3.2.1 Ensuring Data Security and Compliance

The survey results show that respondents employ a range of approaches to ensure data security and compliance with relevant regulations, including the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**. The majority (58.3%) reported relying on **internal protocols and procedures** to manage data protection. A further 41.7% indicated receiving **institutional or organizational support**, such as dedicated policies or IT departments overseeing compliance. A smaller proportion (8.6%) reported using **external consultants or service providers** for these tasks. Notably, 28.6% of respondents stated that their organization or team does **not currently have a clear process** for ensuring data security and compliance. These results reveal varying degrees of formalization and institutional support in the implementation of data protection measures across respondent groups.

3.2.2 Collaboration and Data Sharing Practices

In terms of collaboration and data sharing, respondents most frequently reported **internal sharing within their teams or organizations (73.7%)**, followed by **institutional-level sharing (41.1%)**, which includes data exchange between departments, universities, or other public institutions. 29.7% of respondents stated that they **publicly share** data via open-access platforms or repositories, while 12.6% reported that their data is **not shared with others**. An additional 5.7% selected “other,” referring to specific or restricted data-sharing arrangements. The findings suggest that most data exchange currently occurs within institutional boundaries, with a smaller share of respondents engaging in open data sharing practices.

3.2.3 Willingness to Test New Tools and Platforms

When asked about openness to adopting new tools, platforms, or practices for data management and open science, **46.3%** of respondents stated they would be **willing to test** new approaches. A further **47.4%** indicated that their willingness **depends on timing or relevance**, while **6.3%** were **not interested**. These results show a generally positive attitude toward innovation in data management practices, suggesting a strong potential for participation in pilot initiatives and tool evaluations within the framework of the APPROACH project.

3.2.4 Reflections on Current Data Management Practices

Overall, the findings demonstrate that most respondents have established internal mechanisms for data security and are engaged in collaborative data exchange, primarily within their institutions. However, a notable proportion lacks formalized procedures or does not share data openly. While adoption of open data repositories and tools is not yet widespread, the high degree of willingness to test new platforms and solutions indicates readiness among respondents to further develop and refine their data management practices, provided adequate support and guidance are available.

3.3 Current Practices in Data Management

This section analyses the key challenges and barriers identified by respondents that affect the implementation of **open science** and **data management** practices. It considers practical, institutional, and cultural constraints, including **lack of training, resources, incentives, and time**, as well as **legal and ethical concerns** related to data sharing. The section also reviews the **barriers to participation in training activities**, highlighting factors that limit engagement in capacity-building initiatives. The insights presented here help identify the areas where targeted support and institutional improvements are needed to facilitate open science adoption.

3.3.1 Main Challenges in Adopting Open Science Practices

Respondents identified several key challenges that affect the adoption of open science and data management practices within their organizations. The most frequently reported issue was **lack of training or awareness (56.6%)**, followed by **lack of time or resources (49.7%)**. Other commonly mentioned barriers included **infrastructure or tool limitations (35.4%)**, **lack of incentives (22.9%)**, and **legal or ethical concerns (20.0%)**. A smaller share of respondents cited **cultural resistance (8.0%)** and **other issues (4.6%)** such as unclear institutional procedures or limited access to appropriate

platforms. These findings highlight a combination of structural, technical, and motivational challenges in implementing open science practices.

3.3.2 Legal, Ethical, and Privacy Concerns

The survey explored whether privacy or legal constraints prevent respondents from sharing data. 30.3% of participants indicated that such concerns do indeed restrict data sharing within their organizations, while 69.7% stated that they do not face these limitations. The responses show that while legal and ethical compliance is a consideration for some, it is not a universal barrier across all respondents. Nonetheless, the presence of such concerns among nearly one-third of participants suggests the need for clearer guidance on data protection and responsible data sharing.

3.3.3 Barriers to Participation in Training

When asked about potential barriers that could prevent participation in open science or data management training, the most common response was **lack of time** (76.0%). Other limiting factors included **lack of incentives or motivation** (32.0%), **perceived lack of relevance** (28.6%), **language or accessibility issues** (15.4%), and **technical or digital skills gaps** (14.3%). A small proportion (3.4%) cited other personal or organizational constraints. These results indicate that time availability and perceived relevance are the most significant factors influencing training participation.

3.3.4 Institutional and Organizational Limitations

Institutional capacity also appears to play an important role in enabling or restricting open science adoption. The combined challenges of limited time, insufficient resources, and lack of training opportunities suggest that many organizations may not yet have fully integrated open science principles into their operational or research frameworks. The identified lack of incentives further implies that open science activities are not always formally recognized or rewarded, which may discourage wider engagement.

3.3.5 Reflections on Challenges and Barriers

Overall, the findings reveal a complex set of barriers that hinder the broader adoption of open science and data management practices. While awareness of the concept is high, structural and resource-related limitations remain significant. The results point to a clear need for institutional support in the

form of **targeted training, simplified tools, dedicated resources, and incentive structures** that can facilitate the transition toward more open and standardized research practices.

3.4 Perceived Benefits and Opportunities

This section summarizes respondents' perceptions of the potential benefits and opportunities arising from the implementation of **open science** and **data management** practices. It identifies the most frequently cited advantages, such as improved transparency, collaboration, and innovation, and outlines the **sectors perceived to benefit most** from enhanced data sharing. Additionally, it examines respondents' views on **motivating factors** that could promote the wider adoption of open science, including training, simplified tools, and institutional incentives. These findings help to illustrate the perceived value of open science across disciplines and sectors.

3.4.1 Benefits of Open Science and Data Management

Respondents identified a range of benefits associated with the implementation of open science and data management practices. The most frequently mentioned advantage was improved transparency (66.3%), followed by faster innovation (62.9%) and increased collaboration (58.9%). Other reported benefits included broader societal impact (38.3%) and policy alignment (21.7%). A small number of respondents (2.9%) indicated other benefits, such as improved reproducibility and greater visibility of research outputs. These findings suggest that participants generally associate open science with enhanced cooperation, innovation, and public trust in research outcomes.

3.4.2 Sectors Benefiting from Open Science and Data Sharing

When asked which sectors could benefit most from improved data sharing and open science, respondents most frequently selected health and medical research (76.6%). This was followed by environmental science and climate research (62.3%), education and academia (60.0%), energy and sustainability (58.3%), and industry and innovation (57.1%). Other areas identified as beneficiaries included technology and engineering (54.3%), crisis and disaster response (48.0%), agriculture and food systems (42.3%), and public policy and governance (32.6%). Smaller proportions mentioned social sciences and humanities (33.1%) and cultural heritage and arts (21.7%). The broad range of sectors highlighted underscores the perceived cross-disciplinary relevance of open science.

3.4.3 Motivations for Adopting Open Science Practices

In relation to factors that could encourage wider adoption of open science practices, respondents emphasized the importance of simplified tools and platforms (62.3%) and more guidance and training (60.6%). Other motivating factors included incentives (41.7%) and stronger mandates (18.9%), while 5.7% selected other drivers such as clearer institutional frameworks or peer influence.

These responses indicate that practical support and training are viewed as key enablers of open science adoption, alongside organizational incentives.

3.4.4 Reflections on Benefits and Opportunities

Overall, respondents demonstrated a clear understanding of the potential benefits of open science, particularly in fostering transparency, collaboration, and innovation. The wide range of sectors identified as potential beneficiaries reflects the versatility and applicability of open science principles across disciplines. However, the emphasis on the need for simpler tools, targeted training, and stronger institutional support suggests that the realization of these benefits depends on addressing existing practical and structural barriers.

3.5 Training Needs and Participation Preferences

This section focuses on the training needs and participation preferences of respondents in relation to **open science** and **data management**. It identifies the most relevant **topics of interest**, **preferred formats and delivery methods**, and **barriers to participation** in training initiatives. Furthermore, it explores respondents' **willingness to contribute** to the development and testing of new training materials and tools within European initiatives such as the APPROACH project. The section concludes with reflections on how training activities can be better aligned with participants' expectations, availability, and learning preferences.

3.5.1 Topics of Interest for Open Science and Data Management Training

Respondents expressed a strong interest in a range of topics related to open science and data management. The most frequently selected areas were **practical tools for data sharing** (58.3%) and **FAIR data principles** (56.6%), followed by **collaborative platforms and workflows** (52.0%) and **licensing and legal issues** (49.7%). Other areas of interest included **case studies or real-world examples** (34.3%) and **ethical and responsible data handling** (33.7%). These results suggest a clear demand for applied, practice-oriented training that combines technical knowledge with practical case-based learning.

3.5.2 Preferred Formats and Delivery Methods for Training Activities

In terms of preferred training formats, participants demonstrated a clear preference for **short videos or microlearning** (56.0%) and **online self-paced modules** (45.1%). Other popular options included **live online webinars or sessions** (40.0%), **in-person workshops or seminars** (29.1%), and **blended**

formats combining online and in-person components (26.3%). Only a small number (1.1%) selected other formats. These results indicate a preference for flexible, accessible, and time-efficient learning opportunities that can accommodate different professional schedules and learning styles.

3.5.3 Barriers to Participation in Training

When asked about factors that could prevent participation in open science or data management training, the most frequently cited barrier was **lack of time (76.0%)**. Additional challenges included **lack of incentives or motivation (32.0%)**, **perceived lack of relevance to work (28.6%)**, **language or accessibility issues (15.4%)**, and **technical or digital skills gaps (14.3%)**. A small proportion (3.4%) reported other personal or organizational obstacles. These findings highlight that even when training opportunities are available, practical constraints, especially time, remain a major limiting factor for engagement.

3.5.4 Interest in Contributing to Development and Testing of New Tools and Training

The survey also explored respondents' willingness to participate in future European initiatives related to open science and data management. **20.0%** of participants expressed definite interest in contributing to the **development, testing, or evaluation** of new tools and training under projects such as **APPROACH**. A further **32.6%** indicated conditional interest, depending on timing and relevance, while **47.4%** stated that they were not currently interested. These results show a moderate level of engagement potential among respondents, particularly among those already familiar with open science concepts.

3.5.5 Reflections on Training Needs and Participation Preferences

The findings reveal a strong and widespread demand for **practical, flexible, and easily accessible training opportunities** on open science and data management. Respondents favor short, targeted learning modules and online formats that allow them to learn at their own pace. While interest in participation is high, barriers such as time constraints and limited institutional incentives remain key challenges. Addressing these issues—through modular content, flexible delivery, and recognition mechanisms—would help to enhance participation and build sustainable capacity for open science implementation across sectors.

4 Main findings and recommendations

4.1 Summary of Main Findings

The survey results demonstrate a generally positive attitude toward open science and data management among respondents, alongside significant variation in awareness, understanding, and implementation.

Overall, awareness of open science concepts is high (71.8%), yet practical engagement and formal training remain uneven. While nearly half of respondents (45.1%) have participated in some form of training, the majority (54.9%) have not, indicating that structured educational opportunities are still limited across sectors and countries.

A substantial proportion of respondents (48.0%) are involved in handling scientific data daily, suggesting a strong foundation for future capacity-building initiatives. However, awareness and application of FAIR data principles are inconsistent—only 21.7% actively apply them, while 28.0% are unfamiliar. Similarly, 40.6% use data management repositories such as Zenodo or GitHub, leaving a majority without standardized tools for data storage and sharing.

When it comes to compliance, most respondents rely on internal protocols (58.3%) or institutional support (41.7%), though nearly one-third (28.6%) report having no clear process for data security or GDPR compliance. Collaboration remains largely internal, with 73.7% sharing data within their organizations but only 29.7% doing so publicly. Nevertheless, openness to innovation is high, with 46.3% willing and 47.4% conditionally willing to test new data management tools or platforms.

The most frequently cited barriers to adopting open science practices include lack of training or awareness (56.6%), lack of time or resources (49.7%), and infrastructure limitations (35.4%). Legal and ethical concerns (20.0%) and the absence of incentives (22.9%) were also noted. Despite these challenges, respondents recognized several important benefits of open science, including improved transparency (66.3%), faster innovation (62.9%), and increased collaboration (58.9%).

Awareness of supportive frameworks remains limited, with only 20.0% of respondents familiar with EU or national policies on open science. This gap indicates that further communication and institutional alignment are required to support policy-driven implementation.

Training-related findings reveal strong interest in practical, accessible, and flexible learning approaches. The most popular topics were FAIR data principles (56.6%), data sharing tools (58.3%), and collaborative platforms (52.0%), while preferred formats included short videos or microlearning (56.0%) and self-paced online modules (45.1%). Time constraints (76.0%) were identified as the main barrier to participation.

In summary, the findings indicate broad conceptual support for open science but highlight the need for practical training, simplified tools, and institutional incentives to enable consistent adoption across stakeholder groups.

4.2 Key Conclusions

The findings of the survey indicate that awareness of open science is high among respondents, but practical implementation remains limited. Many participants understand the concept but lack the necessary training, institutional guidance, or tools to integrate open science into their daily work. Over half of respondents have not received formal training, and a significant proportion report the absence of clear internal policies for data management or compliance.

Familiarity with **FAIR data principles** and use of repositories are inconsistent, highlighting the need for targeted education and technical support to improve interoperability and long-term data reusability. The most commonly reported barrier, time constraints, lack of incentives, and limited infrastructure—suggest that both personal and institutional factors inhibit engagement. However, respondents also expressed strong motivation to improve, recognizing the benefits of open science for collaboration, transparency, and innovation, and showing willingness to adopt new tools and participate in future initiatives.

4.3 Recommendations

In light of these findings, several recommendations emerge for strengthening open science and data management practices within the framework of the **APPROACH project** and beyond.

First, **awareness and communication** around open science should be enhanced. Greater dissemination of information about EU and national policies, as well as visibility of successful case studies and good practices, can help bridge existing knowledge gaps. Consistent communication strategies can also strengthen engagement among stakeholders across research, business, and policy sectors.

Second, **training and capacity building** should be expanded and diversified. A modular training program that includes topics such as FAIR data principles, open access publishing, ethical data handling, and repository use would help address the uneven distribution of knowledge. The delivery of training should prioritize flexibility through self-paced online courses, webinars, and short video-based materials that accommodate time constraints. Practical, hands-on exercises and case-based examples should be incorporated to reinforce learning outcomes and promote applicability to participants' professional contexts.

Third, **institutional support and infrastructure** should be improved. Organizations should be encouraged to adopt standardized internal policies for data management and compliance, and to integrate open-source tools such as Zenodo or the Open Science Framework (Foster & Deardorff, 2017) into their daily workflows. Providing access to technical assistance and guidance on metadata standards and repository management would facilitate consistency and reliability in data handling practices.

Fourth, it is important to **create meaningful incentives** for participation in open science. Recognition of open data contributions in performance evaluations, career progression, and research funding schemes would encourage wider engagement. Establishing reward mechanisms or small grants for open data initiatives could further motivate both individuals and institutions to participate.

Finally, a **collaborative and inclusive approach** should be fostered. Researchers, SMEs, policymakers, and educators should be actively involved in co-developing training materials, tools, and guidelines to ensure relevance across sectors. Promoting cross-sector collaboration can bridge the gap between academic and business perspectives, while pilot projects and feedback loops within the APPROACH framework can ensure continuous improvement and validation of tools and training resources.

4.4 Outlook

The survey provides a strong evidence base for future training and policy actions within **Work Package 3** of the APPROACH project. While conceptual awareness of open science is well established, the next phase must focus on transforming this awareness into consistent practice. Developing targeted, flexible training, enhancing institutional frameworks, and fostering cooperation across sectors will be essential steps toward achieving this goal. By addressing these priorities, the project will contribute to building a more open, transparent, and collaborative research culture across Europe, strengthening both scientific excellence and societal impact.

5 Conclusion

The **APPROACH** project's **Work Package 3** aims to improve learning, engagement, talent management, and continuous professional development among researchers and innovators, particularly in the field of **solar energy harvesting**. Within this framework, Deliverable 3.4 sought to identify the current levels of awareness, experience, and attitudes toward **open science** and **data management** among a diverse range of stakeholders, including scientists, SME representatives, policymakers, and members of the public. The survey findings offer an important empirical foundation for understanding how open science principles are being perceived and practiced, as well as for shaping future training activities and institutional strategies across participating countries.

The results demonstrate that while the **concept of open science is widely recognized**, the depth of understanding and the level of practical implementation vary considerably. A substantial majority of respondents (**71.8%**) were familiar with the concept of open science, but only **45.1%** had participated in any related training, and fewer still reported applying its principles in their daily work. Awareness without structured learning opportunities results in fragmented implementation, which underscores the urgent need for **consistent, accessible, and context-sensitive training programs**.

Respondents' levels of engagement with scientific data further illustrate this uneven landscape. Almost half (**48.0%**) handle data on a daily basis, and yet only **21.7%** actively apply the **FAIR data principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), while **28.0%** remain unfamiliar with them. This indicates that while technical engagement with data is common, understanding of open data management standards is not yet widespread. Encouragingly, the interest in learning about these principles is strong, suggesting that targeted interventions could yield significant impact if designed to bridge the existing knowledge-to-practice gap.

Institutional and infrastructural challenges also emerged clearly from the results. The majority of respondents (**58.3%**) rely on **internal protocols** for data security and compliance, and **41.7%** depend on institutional guidance. However, **28.6%** of participants reported the absence of a clear process for ensuring compliance with regulations such as the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**. This finding points to inconsistencies in how organizations interpret and apply data management policies and highlights the need for more harmonized institutional frameworks that integrate open science principles into daily operations.

The survey also confirmed the existence of multiple **barriers to open science adoption**. The most significant among these are **lack of training or awareness (56.6%)**, **time and resource constraints (49.7%)**, and **insufficient infrastructure (35.4%)**. Additional challenges include limited incentives,

legal and ethical concerns, and, in some cases, cultural resistance to change. These obstacles are not unique to any one country or sector but rather reflect a systemic issue across the European research landscape.

Despite these limitations, the perception of open science remains highly positive. Respondents identified clear benefits, including **greater transparency (66.3%)**, **faster innovation (62.9%)**, and **increased collaboration (58.9%)**. These findings demonstrate that stakeholders recognize the potential of open science to improve research efficiency, foster innovation, and enhance the societal relevance of scientific work. The challenge, therefore, is not one of motivation but of capacity—how to translate enthusiasm into sustainable practice through structured support, practical training, and institutional incentives.

The survey also revealed valuable insights into how participants prefer to engage with training. The majority favor **short, modular, and self-paced formats**—such as microlearning videos (**56.0%**) and online courses (**45.1%**)—over traditional in-person sessions. This preference reflects both the time pressures faced by professionals and the increasing normalization of digital learning environments. However, **76.0%** of respondents cited lack of time as the principal barrier to participation, indicating that even well-designed training must be flexible, concise, and closely aligned with participants' professional realities.

In terms of future engagement, the results are encouraging: **46.3%** of respondents expressed willingness, and **47.4%** conditional willingness, to test new tools or platforms supporting open science. Furthermore, one in five participants indicated readiness to contribute to the development and evaluation of new training materials within European initiatives such as **APPROACH**. These findings confirm that the stakeholder community is not only receptive to open science but also willing to actively participate in its advancement, provided appropriate opportunities and support structures are available.

The implications of these findings for the **APPROACH project** and for European research policy more broadly are clear. Open science is both a technical and cultural transformation that requires systemic change. It demands not only new tools and training but also **organizational alignment, institutional commitment, and policy coherence**. Strengthening awareness of national and EU-level frameworks, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and FAIR data mandates, will be essential to creating a unified environment where open science can thrive.

Going forward, **Work Package 3** should focus on developing a **comprehensive training framework** that combines practical skills development with strategic policy understanding. Training materials should integrate real-world case studies, simulations, and examples from solar energy research to ensure

relevance and applicability. Institutional collaboration will be crucial for embedding these practices into everyday research workflows, thereby enhancing not only compliance but also research quality, transparency, and reproducibility.

Ultimately, this deliverable underscores that open science is not merely a set of technical standards but a **collective movement toward more equitable and efficient knowledge sharing**. Its success depends on the engagement of all actors—researchers, administrators, industry professionals, and policymakers—working collaboratively toward shared goals. Through the continued efforts of the APPROACH project, supported by evidence such as this survey, Europe can take significant steps toward realizing a more open, innovative, and inclusive research ecosystem.

Executive Summary of Key Messages:

1. High Awareness, Limited Implementation:

While 71.8% of respondents are familiar with open science, fewer than half have received formal training or apply its principles in practice.

2. Inconsistent Data Management Practices:

Only 21.7% actively apply FAIR principles, and nearly 30% are unfamiliar with them, indicating a strong need for targeted education.

3. Institutional Gaps in Compliance:

Around one-third of respondents lack clear processes for data security and GDPR compliance, underscoring the need for harmonized institutional frameworks.

4. Key Barriers Identified:

The main obstacles include lack of training (56.6%), limited time and resources (49.7%), and inadequate infrastructure (35.4%).

5. Positive Perception of Benefits:

Open science is widely valued for its potential to enhance transparency, collaboration, and innovation across sectors.

6. Strong Motivation for Participation:

Nearly half of respondents are willing to test new tools or engage in further training under initiatives such as APPROACH.

7. Need for Flexible Training Models:

Respondents prefer concise, modular, and online learning formats that fit professional schedules and encourage continuous engagement.

8. Strategic Recommendations:

Future actions should focus on building institutional support, expanding training capacity, improving policy alignment, and creating incentives to sustain engagement.

5.1 Final Remarks

The findings presented in this report underscore both the progress achieved and the challenges that remain in advancing open science and data management practices across Europe. The **APPROACH project**, through Work Package 3, has taken important steps toward understanding the current landscape, identifying knowledge gaps, and designing targeted interventions to support researchers, innovators, and institutions in adopting open and transparent research methodologies.

This survey has provided a solid empirical foundation upon which future training programs, workshops, and policy actions can be built. The evidence demonstrates that while awareness of open science is strong, genuine and sustainable implementation will depend on the creation of an enabling environment that combines **training, institutional commitment, policy alignment, and incentive structures**.

Looking forward, the project's continued efforts will play a vital role in supporting Europe's transition toward a more **collaborative, transparent, and innovation-driven research ecosystem**. By reinforcing open science as a shared standard of excellence, the APPROACH project contributes not only to improving research quality but also to ensuring that scientific knowledge serves society in the most effective and equitable way possible.

Appendix 1 Survey questionnaire

The following questions were included in the Open Science and Data Management Survey conducted as part of **Work Package 3 (WP3)** of the **APPROACH project**. The questionnaire aimed to identify and benchmark the experiences, preferences, and situations related to open science and data management among researchers, SMEs, academics, policymakers, and other stakeholders

Consent

All questions were designed to be **voluntary and anonymous**, ensuring participants' privacy and compliance with GDPR standards. At the beginning of the questionnaire, participants were informed about the survey's purpose and provided digital consent to participate via **Webropol**.

Survey template

1.	What is your professional background?

2.	What is your primary country of residence or work?

3.	Have you heard of the concept of open science?
	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure

4.	Have you previously participated in any data management or open science training?
	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No

5.	What is your level of involvement with scientific data?
	<input type="radio"/> Daily <input type="radio"/> Occasionally <input type="radio"/> Rarely

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Not at all
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6.	What are the main challenges you or your organization face in adopting open science and data management?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of training or awareness ○ Legal or ethical concerns ○ Infrastructure/tools limitations ○ Lack of incentives ○ Lack of time/resources ○ Cultural resistance ○ Other (please specify)

7.	Which benefits do you see in implementing open science practices?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased collaboration ○ Improved transparency ○ Faster innovation ○ Broader societal impact ○ Policy alignment ○ Other (please specify)

8.	In your opinion, what sectors could benefit most from improved data sharing and open science?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Health and medical research ○ Environmental science and climate research ○ Agriculture and food systems ○ Education and academia ○ Energy and sustainability ○ Public policy and governance ○ Technology and engineering ○ Social sciences and humanities ○ Industry and innovation (e.g., SMEs, R&D) ○ Industry and innovation (e.g., SMEs, R&D) ○ Cultural heritage and arts

	<input type="radio"/> Other (please specify)
9.	Are there privacy or legal concerns that prevent you from sharing data?
	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
10.	What would encourage you to adopt open science practices more widely?
	<input type="radio"/> Incentives <input type="radio"/> Simplified tools and platforms <input type="radio"/> More guidance-training <input type="radio"/> Stronger mandates <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify)
11.	Are you aware of any EU or national policies supporting open science or data sharing?
	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure
12.	Do you currently use any data management tools or repositories (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub)?
	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
13.	Are you familiar with, or do you currently follow, any of the FAIR data principles in your work? <i>(FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable – principles that help make data easier to locate, use, and share in a meaningful and standardized way.)</i>
	<input type="radio"/> Yes - I actively apply them <input type="radio"/> Yes - I am aware of them but don't fully understand them <input type="radio"/> No - I have heard the term but don't fully understand them <input type="radio"/> No - I am not familiar with the FAIR principles <input type="radio"/> Not applicable to my work

14.	<p>How do you ensure data security and compliance (e.g., GDPR) in your work or organization? <i>(This refers to how you protect data from unauthorized access and ensure compliance with data protection regulations such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR.)</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Internal protocols and procedures <input type="radio"/> Institutional or organizational support <input type="radio"/> External consultants or service providers <input type="radio"/> We don't currently have a clear process <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify)

15.	<p>Would you be open to testing new tools, platforms, or practices for data management and open science in your work or organization?</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Maybe / It depends

16.	<p>How do you currently collaborate or share research or project-related data with others? <i>(This refers to how you exchange data within your team or with external partners.)</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Internal sharing within my team or organization <input type="radio"/> Institutional-level sharing (e.g., across departments, universities, or public institutions) <input type="radio"/> Publicly shared (e.g., open access platforms, repositories) <input type="radio"/> Data is not shared with others <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify):

17.	<p>What topics would you find most useful in open science and data management training?</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) <input type="radio"/> Licensing and legal issues (e.g., copyright, data ownership, open licenses) <input type="radio"/> Practical tools for data sharing (e.g., repositories, file formats, metadata) <input type="radio"/> Collaborative platforms and workflows (e.g., GitHub, OSF, shared drives) <input type="radio"/> Ethical and responsible data handling <input type="radio"/> Case studies or real-world examples <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify):

18.	What is your preferred format for participating in training sessions or workshops?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Online self-paced modules ○ Live online webinars or sessions ○ In-person workshops or seminars ○ Blended formats (a mix of online and in-person) ○ Short videos or micro learning (5–10 min videos) ○ Other (please specify):

19.	What barriers might prevent you from participating in open science or data management training?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of time ○ Perceived lack of relevance to my work ○ Lack of incentives or motivation ○ Technical difficulties or digital skills gaps ○ Language or accessibility issues ○ Other (please specify):

20.	Would you be interested in contributing further to the development, testing, or evaluation of new open science and data management tools or training as part of a European initiative (e.g., the APPROACH project)?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Yes – I’m interested and would like to be contacted. Please optionally provide your email address: ○ Maybe – I would consider it depending on timing and relevance. Please optionally provide your email address: ○ No – I’m not interested at this time.

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Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee Process

Strategy document

Deliverable Lead:

Deliverable due date: 30.11.2025

Actual submission date:

Version: 1.0

This project receives funding in the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research Programme under Grant Agreement Number 101120397

Document Control Page	
Title	Knowledge Sharing - Interactive Employee Process, Strategy document
Creator	Vaasa University of Applied Sciences
Description	This strategy document focuses on enhancing knowledge sharing practices among employees within organisations. It builds on insights from desktop research and survey findings and represents the third stage of Task 3.5. The task comprises three main activities: (A) investigation of current knowledge sharing practices, (B) piloting knowledge sharing practices, and (C) development of this strategy document.
Creation date	25.11.2025
Type	Strategy document
Language	English
Audience	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> public <input type="checkbox"/> confidential
Review status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by Partners <input type="checkbox"/> for approval by the WP leader <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for approval by the Project Coordinator

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DISCLAIMER

The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the APPROACH project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.

DISCLOSURE OF USE OF AI-BASED TECHNOLOGIES

M365 Copilot and ChatGPT have been used to support the drafting and editing of this document. The authors have reviewed, verified, and are responsible for all content.

Abstract

This strategy document is part of Task 3.5: Knowledge Sharing – Interactive Employee Process within the APPROACH project. Task 3.5 consists of three stages: (A) investigation of current knowledge sharing practices, (B) piloting interactive practices, and (C) development of this strategy document. Building on insights from desktop research and survey findings, this document provides guidance for improving knowledge sharing between employees, both within and across teams. It sets the direction for implementing effective practices and supporting organisational enablers, methods, and digital tools that foster interaction and the exchange of experiences, expertise, ideas, and information.

I Introduction

This document represents the third and final stage of Task 3.5 Knowledge Sharing – Interactive Employee Process, which comprises three interconnected activities: (A) investigating current knowledge sharing practices, (B) piloting interactive knowledge sharing practices, and (C) developing a strategy document (see Figure 1). As the outcome of stage C, this strategy document builds on the findings of the first two stages and synthesises the insights gained throughout the process.

In stage A, a desktop research and survey were conducted to explore how employees share knowledge within and across teams in different organisational settings. The results of this investigation provided an empirical foundation for identifying relevant knowledge sharing behaviours, enablers and barriers, and informed the design of the pilot activities. Stage B involved piloting selected interactive methods, tools and platforms. These pilots focused on human-centred and experiential learning approaches to promote knowledge exchange and enhance collaboration between employees. Where relevant, elements of design thinking were incorporated to support iterative learning and problem solving

In this final stage, stage C, the findings from the research and pilot activities are integrated into a comprehensive strategy document. The purpose of the strategy is to present key insights, highlight effective practices, and offer actionable recommendations for improving knowledge sharing between employees within organisations. Beyond supporting the objectives of the APPROACH project, this document also serves as a resource for other organisations seeking to strengthen their knowledge sharing culture.

Figure 1 Key activities in implementation of Task 3.5

The structure of this document is as follows: After the introduction, Chapter 2, “What is Knowledge Sharing?”, provides the conceptual basis for the strategy. It defines knowledge and knowledge sharing, emphasising their role in organisational learning, innovation, and performance. The chapter distinguishes between explicit and tacit knowledge and explores the behavioural dimensions of sharing, such as donating and collecting knowledge. It also examines enablers and barriers to knowledge sharing, including trust, reciprocity, and cultural factors, while addressing counterproductive behaviours like hoarding, hiding, and sabotage.

Chapter 3, “Organisational Knowledge Sharing Enablers,” focuses on structural and cultural factors that support knowledge exchange. It introduces formal and informal practices and highlights leadership, incentives, and organisational processes as critical enablers. The chapter also presents two key subsets of practices: interactive methods such as mentoring, workshops, and brainstorming and digital tools, including collaboration platforms and document management systems. Furthermore, it discusses approaches for measuring the effectiveness of knowledge sharing through behavioural indicators and organisational metrics.

Chapter 4, “Good Knowledge Sharing Practices,” moves from theory to practice by showcasing examples identified through surveys and workshops within the APPROACH project. It illustrates how partner organisations combine digital tools with social and collaborative methods to foster knowledge flow. The chapter also addresses cultural factors influencing success and offers recommendations for creating environments where knowledge sharing thrives. Emphasis is placed on trust, psychological safety, and leadership engagement as prerequisites for effective practices.

Finally, Chapter 5, “Summing Up: Becoming a Knowledge Sharing Organisation,” synthesises the insights gained throughout the document. It underscores that becoming a knowledge sharing organisation is not merely a technical exercise but a strategic and cultural transformation. The chapter outlines actionable recommendations, including embedding knowledge sharing into organisational culture, establishing structured processes, developing centralised repositories, strengthening digital competence, diversifying methods, and implementing recognition systems. These steps aim to ensure that knowledge sharing becomes an integral and sustainable part of organisational life.

2 What is Knowledge Sharing?

2.1 Knowledge Sharing in Organisations

Knowledge is an essential resource for organisations, providing them with a sustainable competitive advantage in dynamic and competitive business environment (Wang & Noe, 2010; Yi, 2009). Knowledge sharing, as a pivotal knowledge management activity, can bring significant benefits to an organisation, such as fostering innovation and organisational learning, developing new skills and capabilities, and increasing productivity (Castaneda & Cuellar, 2020; Jackson et al., 2006; Mueller, 2015). Knowledge sharing between employees enables organisations to exploit their knowledge-based resources (Wang & Noe, 2010). It links individuals and organisations by transferring knowledge from an individual to an organisational level, thereby creating competitive value for the organisation (Ipe, 2003).

Knowledge sharing is a critical enabler of innovation, as innovation depends on organisations' ability to utilise employees' knowledge, skills, and experience during organisational value creation processes. Effective knowledge sharing practices not only foster idea generation and organisational learning but also enable to respond rapidly to evolving market opportunities and customer needs. Ultimately, innovation outcomes depend on both the knowledge sharing practices that organisations implement, as well as on the willingness of employees to participate actively in such activities. (Singh et al., 2021.)

Despite the numerous definitions of knowledge sharing, researchers and practitioners have not reached a consensus on its precise meaning, leaving a gap not only in defining the concept but also in determining the types of knowledge that should be shared (Yeboah, 2023). In our research, we adopted the definition provided by Yeboah (2023: 38), which states that “knowledge sharing is employee-to-employee learning procedure to assist one another to enhance their potential, solve problems and boost work performance”

Simply put, *knowledge sharing* refers to the process by which knowledge is communicated or transmitted to others (Jackson et al., 2006), involving capturing or moving knowledge from a source to a recipient (Bircham-Connolly et al., 2005). This process encompasses two key dimensions: the willingness of individuals to actively disseminate their knowledge to others (i.e., knowledge donating), and their active efforts to acquire knowledge from others to learn from them (i.e., knowledge collecting) (Lin, 2007). During this process, knowledge held by an individual is converted into a form that can be understood, absorbed, and used by other individuals (Hong et al., 2011; Ipe, 2003).

Knowledge sharing inherently involves a relationship between at least two parties: one who holds the knowledge and another who receives or acquires it. The use of the term *sharing* suggests that the act of presenting individual knowledge in a form accessible to others involves deliberate and conscious effort by the knowledge holder. Furthermore, sharing implies that the originator does not relinquish ownership of the knowledge; rather, it leads to a form of joint ownership between the sender and the recipient. (Ipe, 2003.)

The *knowledge* shared by individuals can be *explicit or tacit* (Bartol & Srivastava, 2002; Ipe, 2003). According to this dominant classification, originally introduced by Polanyi (1966) and further explained by Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), tacit knowledge is personal, experiential, and often subconscious, which makes it difficult to articulate or codify. It includes skills, intuition, and know-how that are typically acquired through practice. In contrast, explicit knowledge is formal, systematic, and easily communicated or documented, such as in manuals, databases, or written procedures. Knowledge is a complex and multifaced construct that encompasses more than just information or data. It is “a fluid mix” of experience, values, contextual information, and expert insights, which together provide a framework for evaluating and applying new experiences and information (Davenport & Prusak, 1998).

Therefore, knowledge sharing involves social interactions between individuals through which experiences, skills, and both explicit and tacit knowledge are exchanged (Castaneda & Cuellar, 2020). Within organisations, it refers to the process where employees exchange their work-related experience, expertise, know-how, and contextual information (Lin, 2007). During this process employees share organisationally relevant information, ideas, suggestions, and expertise with one another (Bartol & Srivastava, 2002).

Knowledge can be shared at the individual, group and organisational levels, either within or across organisations (Ipe, 2003). In the APPROACH project, we focus on knowledge sharing practices at group level, between individuals in organisations. Furthermore, we examine knowledge sharing practices, that facilitate interaction between employees, both in and across teams. According to Katzenbach and Smith (1993: 45), a *team* is defined as: “a small number of people with complementary skills who are committed to a common purpose, performance goals and an approach for which they hold themselves mutually accountable.” Some scholars make a distinction between teams and groups (e.g., Katzenbach & Smith, 1993). However, as with Kozlowski and Bell (2003), these terms can be used interchangeably, bearing in mind that teams and groups can vary widely in type and size, spanning different contexts, functions, internal processes, and external linkages.

Work teams, in particular, consist of two or more individuals who come together to perform organisationally relevant tasks. They share one or more common goals, exhibit task interdependence (in terms of workflow, goals, knowledge, and outcomes), and interact socially—either face-to-face or virtually. These teams manage their own boundaries while being embedded in a broader organisational context that defines their limits, constrains their functioning, and shapes interactions with other units. (Kozlowski & Bell, 2003.) Examples of work teams include functional teams, cross-functional teams, project teams and virtual teams.

2.2 Enablers and Barriers of Knowledge Sharing Behaviour

This chapter describes the enablers (drivers) and barriers (triggers) of knowledge sharing behaviour, drawing on insights from Thomas's (2025) qualitative research. Enablers are factors that enable individuals, teams, or organisations to share knowledge productively. This section addresses knowledge sharing at both team and organisational levels. Barriers cause counterproductive behaviour inhibiting knowledge sharing including knowledge hoarding (keeping knowledge to oneself instead of sharing it), hiding (deliberately withholding or concealing requested knowledge) and sabotage (intentionally providing false, misleading, or harmful knowledge).

In the knowledge management literature, there is a greater focus on knowledge sharing enablers than on barriers (Yeboah, 2023). The following table summarises the enablers and barriers of knowledge sharing behaviour at the team and organisational levels, as identified by Thomas (2025) (see Table 1). These levels are described in the following chapters.

Table 1 Enablers and barriers of knowledge sharing at team and organisational level (derived from Thomas, 2025)

	Team level	Organisational level
Enablers (drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared goals & collaboration • Trust & reciprocity • Efficiency & digital tools • Virtual workspaces & knowledge flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership & culture • Incentives & recognition • Structured processes & work environment
Barriers (triggers) Knowledge hoarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust issues/reciprocity • Favouritism & knowledge gatekeeping • Selective virtual collaboration hoarding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workplace politics • Job market uncertainty • Lack of recognition & structural barriers • Virtual non-documentation trap
Knowledge hiding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of reciprocity • Exclusionary behaviours • Selective knowledge networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business strategy • Workplace culture • Cloud-based selective knowledge concealment
Knowledge sabotage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power struggles • Closed knowledge networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership manipulation • Knowledge monopolies

2.2.1 Knowledge Sharing Enablers

At the team level, shared goals and collaboration, trust and reciprocity, efficiency and digital tools, and virtual workspaces and knowledge flow all play a central role in shaping knowledge sharing behaviours.

- *Shared Goals & Collaboration* – Shared goals and a collective vision strengthen knowledge sharing behaviours, as team members recognise the mutual benefits of exchanging information and expertise. Collaboration fosters a reciprocal and efficient process, where aligned teams work more effectively and individual success is linked to collective achievements.
- *Trust and Reciprocity* – Trust and reciprocity are essential for fostering open knowledge sharing, as they create a collaborative environment where team members freely exchange information. Without these, individuals may become guarded, sharing less when their contributions are not reciprocated.

- *Efficiency & Digital Tools* – Knowledge sharing enhances efficiency by reducing redundant work and improving productivity. Digital tools, such as Confluence, Slack, and shared drives, organise information and make it easier to retrieve, thereby improving productivity and collaboration among remote teams.
- *Virtual workspaces & knowledge flow* – Virtual platforms like Slack, Microsoft Teams, and SharePoint enable real-time collaboration and streamline knowledge sharing across remote or distributed teams. However, because communications in these platforms can be ephemeral, teams need structured documentation—such as recording important meetings or archiving knowledge sharing sessions – to preserve and make knowledge easily retrievable.

At the organisational level, leadership encouragement, structured processes, incentives and corporate culture play a pivotal role in fostering knowledge sharing behaviours.

- *Leadership & culture* – Leadership shapes the tone for a knowledge sharing culture, with supportive leaders encouraging open exchange and organisational culture influencing whether employees share or withhold knowledge. A secure, committed, and well-supported workforce fosters free knowledge exchange, reducing tendencies toward hoarding or sabotage.
- *Incentives and recognition* – Incentives and recognition encourage employees to share knowledge by providing tangible benefits and reinforcing positive behaviour. However, excessive reliance on competitive extrinsic rewards can backfire, prompting employees to withhold knowledge for personal gain.
- *Structured processes and work environment* – Structured processes, such as training programs and documentation systems, enhance knowledge sharing by ensuring continuous updates and combining formal and informal learning opportunities. Additionally, workspace design influences knowledge flow, with open layouts promoting collaboration and spontaneous idea exchange, while closed or fragmented spaces can hinder interaction.

2.2.2 Knowledge Hoarding, Hiding and Sabotage

Knowledge hoarding, hiding and sabotage are triggered by structural, relational and psychological factors. Following insights illustrate how workplace conditions, digital practices and social dynamics can restrict knowledge flow and undermine collaborative intent.

Knowledge Hoarding

At the team level, knowledge hoarding is influenced by trust, reciprocity, favouritism, and selective collaboration, with employees weighing potential benefits before deciding to share, which can restrict knowledge flow.

- *Trust issues and reciprocity* – At the team level, lack of trust and perceived imbalance in knowledge exchange lead employees to withhold information, as they assess fairness before sharing.
- *Favouritism and knowledge gatekeeping* – favouritism, hierarchical control, and strategic power play drive team-level knowledge hoarding, as employees and managers restrict information to maintain authority, respond to exclusion, or gain competitive advantage.
- *Selective virtual collaboration hoarding* – In virtual teams, reduced face-to-face interactions make it easier for employees to hoard knowledge selectively, sharing only within trusted circles through private channels or side communications.

At the organisational level, knowledge hoarding is influenced by workplace politics, uncertain job prospects, recognition gaps, inefficient knowledge sharing policies and virtual workspaces.

- *Workplace politics and job market uncertainty* – Workplace politics and job market uncertainty drive organisational-level knowledge hoarding, as employees withhold information to protect their position, navigate power struggles, and safeguard themselves during economic instability.
- *Lack of recognition and structural barriers* – Lack of recognition and structural barriers lead employees to hoard knowledge, as they become more selective in sharing when their contributions are undervalued or unacknowledged.
- *Virtual non-documentation trap* – Lack of structured documentation in virtual meetings and digital interactions can unintentionally lead to knowledge hoarding, as information is either lost, inaccessible, or recorded without being effectively shared.

Knowledge Hiding

At the team level, knowledge hiding is influenced by trust issues, concerns about reciprocity, exclusionary behaviours and selective sharing within subgroups.

- *Reciprocity and exclusionary behaviour* – Lack of reciprocity and exclusionary behaviour drive team-level knowledge hiding, as employees withhold or selectively share information to maintain control, ensure indispensability, and protect themselves from being exploited.
- *Selective knowledge networks* – Selective knowledge networks arise when employees form subgroups based on social or cultural comfort zones, leading to siloed information sharing and private channels that limit trust and equitable knowledge flow within teams.

At the organisational level, knowledge hiding is often driven by business strategy, hierarchical control, workplace politics and concerns about confidentiality. Employees may withhold information not for personal gain but to align with broader organisational policies and protect sensitive data.

- *Business strategy* – Employees engage in knowledge hiding to protect business strategy, withholding information that could advantage competitors or external stakeholders to safeguard organisational interests.
- *Workplace culture and hierarchical structures* – Workplace culture and hierarchical structures influence knowledge hiding by promoting selective sharing, fostering independent work, reinforcing power dynamics, and imposing confidentiality or policy constraints that limit open information exchange.
- *Cloud-based selective knowledge concealment* – Cloud-based platforms, while designed for collective knowledge sharing, can be misused to conceal information by restricting access to select folders, creating the appearance of openness while limiting actual availability.

Knowledge Sabotage

Within teams, knowledge sabotage takes the form of power struggles, exclusionary behaviours and strategic knowledge manipulation.

- *Power struggles* – Power struggles drive team-based knowledge sabotage, as members restrict or manipulate information to consolidate influence, control decision-making, and gain competitive advantage over colleagues.
- *Closed knowledge networks* – Closed knowledge networks emerge when employees restrict information to a trusted inner circle, creating dependency, limiting cross-team collaboration, and fostering inefficiencies and workplace silos.

At the organisational level, knowledge sabotage becomes a structural issue embedded in corporate politics, leadership manipulation and competitive business strategies.

- *Leadership manipulation* – Leadership manipulation drives knowledge sabotage, as leaders and employees use misinformation, selective control, and gaslighting to maintain authority, shape perceptions, and reinforce power, creating an environment of distrust and limiting collaborative knowledge sharing.
- *Knowledge monopolies* – Knowledge monopolies occur when organisations or leaders restrict internal knowledge access to maintain control or create elite circles, leading to inefficiencies, workplace inequalities, distrust, and stifled collaboration, even when external knowledge concealment is strategically justified.

3 Organisational Knowledge Sharing Enablers?

3.1 Knowledge Sharing Practices

In our research, we focused on knowledge sharing practices – methods and tools – that enable employees to communicate, collaborate and work interactively in organisations. Knowledge sharing practices are the structured activities and organisational arrangements that facilitate the exchange of relevant knowledge among employees to enhance innovation, organisational learning and performance at all levels of the organisation (Singh et al., 2021). Knowledge sharing practices are also called knowledge sharing “mechanisms” (Bartol & Srivastava, 2002; Steffen et al., 2017), “opportunities” (Ipe, 2003) and “approaches” (Yang, 2004) within the knowledge management literature.

Knowledge sharing in organisations requires both formal and informal practices (Ipe, 2003; Okhuysen & Eisenhardt, 2002). *Formal knowledge sharing practices* are structured, deliberate mechanisms – such as training programs, structured work teams, and technology-based knowledge systems – designed to facilitate knowledge acquisition and dissemination. They are also called “formal interactions” or “purposive learning channels.” *Informal knowledge sharing practices* are unstructured, socially driven interactions that arise naturally through personal relationships and social networks within the organisation. These are sometimes referred to as “relational learning channels” and facilitate knowledge exchange through trust, social ties, and casual collaboration.

Drawing on previous knowledge management research, we identified two subsets of interactive and collaborative knowledge sharing practices, presented in the subsequent chapters: (1) *Interactive Methods* and (2) *Digital Tools*.

3.1.1 Methods

Table 2 provides an overview of interactive methods for knowledge sharing drawn from the knowledge management literature. By interactive methods, we mean techniques or events that facilitate knowledge sharing between employees, whether online or face-to-face. They are employee-centred practices focused on reciprocal communication, collaboration, active participation, and experiential learning, making them highly effective for transferring tacit knowledge (skills, insights, and experiences that are hard to codify).

Knowledge sharing is rooted in the social interactions through which people work and collaborate. Social activities and informal networks, such as mentoring, joint events, and any kinds of face-to-face interactions, enhance reciprocal knowledge sharing among employees. Facilitating knowledge sharing

through varied methods is essential, as these interactions increase opportunities for communication, strengthen trust and friendships, and encourage mutual learning. (Yang, 2004.)

Table 2 Interactive methods for knowledge sharing

Method	Description (*)	Reference
1. After Action Review	A review conducted after a project, activity, event, or task in which participants reflect on what happened, why it happened, what went well, what needs improvement, and capture lessons learned to enhance future performance.	(CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; United Nations, 2011)
2. Appreciative Inquiry	A participatory organisational development method that focuses on identifying and building upon an organisation's strengths and exceptional performance to drive positive change and improved performance.	(United Nations, 2011)
3. Brainstorming	A problem solving technique where participants generate a wide range of ideas in a free flowing to solve problems or innovate.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017; Castellano et al., 2017; Fukné-Kokot & Kralj, 2016; Hidalgo & Albors, 2008; Yang, 2004)
4. Benchmarking	A process of improving performance through the continuous identification, understanding, and adaptation of outstanding practices and processes found both inside and outside the organisation, and implementing the results to achieve superior performance.	(Zairi & Majed, 2005)
5. Briefing	A short, focused meeting where information, updates, or instructions are communicated to participants to ensure understanding and coordination (e.g., project briefing, inter-shift briefing).	(Alhaji et al., 2013; Yang, 2004)
6. Case Study	An interactive learning method where participants analyse real or hypothetical scenarios to identify problems, evaluate solutions, and share insights.	(Yang, 2004)

Method	Description (*)	Reference
7. Coaching	A relationship where a coach supports an employee in developing specific skills and performance to achieve targeted goals in a given work situation.	(CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Mazorodze & Buckley, 2020)
8. Communities of Practice	Group of people who share a common interest or expertise in a specific field and regularly collaborate to exchange knowledge, learn together, and improve their practices.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017; CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Matsuo & Aihara, 2022; Mazorodze & Buckley, 2020; Neuenfeldt, 2023; United Nations, 2011)
9. Fishbowl	Facilitates dialogue by having a small group of experts discuss a topic in an inner circle while a larger group observes, listens actively, and joins the conversation when they wish, sharing knowledge and expanding collective understanding.	(United Nations, 2011)
10. How-to Guide	Practical resource that provides step-by-step guidance and suggestions for effectively implementing tasks or projects within a specific area of work.	(United Nations, 2011)
11. Jigsaw	A learning strategy in which participants develop expertise on individual parts of a problem and then share their knowledge with the group to collaboratively assemble a complete understanding.	(United Nations, 2011)
12. Job Rotation	A planned practice in which employees are moved between different roles, tasks, or departments within an organisation over a set period of time to broaden their skills, knowledge, and understanding of the business.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014)
13. Knowledge Café	An activity that fosters open, creative dialogue in an informal setting where participants rotate between tables to share knowledge and experiences, collectively building insights and ideas.	(Lefika & Mearns, 2015; United Nations, 2011)

Method	Description (*)	Reference
14. Knowledge Fairs	An event where multiple experts share information and experiences using visual aids and displays, promoting exchange, learning, and the generation of new ideas.	(CIDA, 2003; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; United Nations, 2011)
15. Lunch and Learn	An informal learning session typically held during lunch breaks (also called brown bag lunches) where employees share expertise or insights on a specific topic.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017)
16. Lessons Learned	Capturing and sharing insights from past experiences—both successes and failures—so that individuals and teams can improve future performance and avoid repeating mistakes.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017)
17. Mentoring	A learning relationship between two employees in which an experienced employee (mentor) shares knowledge, experience, and ideas with a less experienced associate (mentee) to support career development and future roles, based on mutual commitment, respect, and trust.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Mazorodze & Buckley, 2020; Singh et al., 2021; Swap et al., 2001)
18. Meeting	A planned gathering to share information and discuss current problems and potential solutions (e.g., a weekly team meeting).	(CIDA, 2003; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Steffen et al., 2017; Yang, 2004)
19. Mind Mapping	An individual brainstorming technique that visually organises ideas around a central concept, using connected branches to explore associations and generate a structured representation of thoughts.	(Castellano et al., 2017; Fukné-Kokot & Kralj, 2016; Hidalgo & Albors, 2008)
20. Peer Assists	A participatory learning method in which participants share experiences and insights to collaboratively develop context-specific solutions and exchange knowledge for addressing a particular challenge.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017; CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; United Nations, 2011)

Method	Description (*)	Reference
21. Role Play	Experiential learning where participants act out specific scenarios to practice skills, decision-making, or interpersonal interactions in a safe environment.	(Yang, 2004)
22. SCAMPER	A creativity technique that turns one idea into several more ideas by applying strategies of Substitution, Combination, Adaptation, Modification, Putting to other uses, Elimination, and Reversing.	(Fukné-Kokot & Kralj, 2016; Hidalgo & Albors, 2008)
23. Seminar	An occasion when a teacher or expert and a group of people meet to study and discuss something.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Yang, 2004)
24. Shadowing	A learning practice where an employee (often less experienced) closely observes and follows a more experienced colleague during their daily work activities.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017)
25. Six Thinking Hats	A role-playing tool that encourages participants to explore a situation from multiple perspectives by symbolically “wearing” different coloured hats, promoting broader thinking, diverse viewpoints, and better problem solving.	(United Nations, 2011)
26. Stochastic Stimulus	Using randomly chosen words or concepts to trigger metaphorical associations, enabling participants discover novel ideas and associations, and support iterative knowledge transfer.	(Castellano et al., 2017)
27. Storytelling	Uses narratives to share knowledge on events in the form of words and/or images, convey lessons learned, and build shared understanding within an organisation.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Mazorodze & Buckley, 2020; Neuenfeldt, 2023; Sole & Wilson, 2002; Swap et al., 2001; Tobin, 2006; United Nations, 2011; Whyte & Classen, 2012)
28. Training	A process of equipping employees with the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitudes to perform their job	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Majewska &

Method	Description (*)	Reference
	effectively (e.g. on-the-job training, classroom training, and e-learning).	Szulczyńska, 2014; Neuenfeldt, 2023; Singh et al., 2021; Steffen et al., 2017; Yang, 2004)
29. TRIZ	Theory of Inventive Problem Solving is a structured, algorithmic approach to solving system problems that addresses innovation obstacles and complex system challenges to identify the ideal solution for a specific, pre-defined problem.	(Fukné-Kokot & Kralj, 2016; Hidalgo & Albors, 2008)
30. Workshop	Facilitated, hands-on session where participants collaborate to solve problems, share knowledge, or develop skills around a specific topic or challenge.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Yang, 2004)

*) The descriptions were generated using the listed references above, [Cambridge Dictionary](#) and ChatGPT.

3.1.2 Digital Tools

Table 3 offers a summary of digital tools for knowledge sharing identified in the knowledge management literature. By digital tools, we mean software, applications, or electronic resources that facilitate remote knowledge sharing between employees in organisations, both synchronously and asynchronously. Digital tools enable collaboration, social interaction, and information sharing across organisational and geographical boundaries (Choi et al., 2010; Mirzaee & Ghaffari, 2018; Ryan et al., 2010; Yuan et al., 2013).

Such tools are particularly valuable for enabling knowledge exchange and cooperation when employees are geographically dispersed and face-to-face communication is not possible, although they cannot fully replace direct interpersonal interaction (Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014). Digital tools alone do not ensure knowledge sharing or efficiency; their value depends on consistent engagement and proper use by team members (Thomas, 2025).

Table 3 Digital tools for knowledge sharing

Tool	Description (*)	Reference
1. Blog	An online platform for publishing chronological personal commentary, links, or editorial content, serving as a widely accessible and versatile communication tool.	(Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Yuan et al., 2013)
2. Chat	A real-time communication tool that enables instant messaging between individuals or groups.	(Tobin, 2006; Yuan et al., 2013)
3. Collaboration Platform	A digital workspace designed to help groups collaborate more effectively by enabling communication and file sharing (e.g., Microsoft Teams, Slack).	(Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Ryan et al., 2010; Tobin, 2006)
4. Discussion Forum	An online platform where participants post messages to generate dialogue, share ideas, provide feedback, and collaboratively create knowledge, while also supporting informal networking and team building.	(United Nations, 2011; Yuan et al., 2013)
5. Document Management System	Cloud-based storage and collaboration service that allow users to store, access, and share files (e.g., Google Drive, Microsoft OneDrive, Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint).	(Neuenfeldt, 2023; Tobin, 2006)
6. E-mail	A digital tool for transmitting and receiving messages, files, and documents over the internet.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Steffen et al., 2017; Tobin, 2006; Yang, 2004; Yuan et al., 2013)
7. E-newsletter	A regularly distributed electronic publication, typically sent via email, that shares updates, news, and information with targeted organisational audiences.	(Ahmed & Elhag, 2017; Steffen et al., 2017)
8. Extranet	A private network for internal and selected external users that, through secure access, enables information sharing with trusted external parties.	(CIDA, 2003; Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Ryan et al., 2010; Tobin, 2006)
9. Intranet	A private, internal network that provides employees with access to organisational resources, information, and services.	(Lefika & Mearns, 2015; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Ryan et al., 2010; Tobin, 2006; Yang, 2004; Yuan et al., 2013)

Tool	Description (*)	Reference
10. Knowledge Repository/ Database	An online storehouse where knowledge, documents, and best practices are collected, organised, and made accessible.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; CIDA, 2003; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Mazorodze & Buckley, 2020; Ryan et al., 2010; Yuan et al., 2013)
11. Learning Management System	An application that automates the administration, tracking, and reporting of training events (e.g., Moodle, Blackboard Learn, Claroline, Enterprise KnowledgePlatform).	(Cuéllar et al., 2011; Poulova et al., 2015; Tobin, 2006)
12. Note-Taking Software	An application that helps creating, organising, and sharing digital notes in various formats with features like tagging, reminders, and document scanning (e.g., Evernote, Microsoft OneNote, Google Keep, Apple Notes).	(Neuenfeldt, 2023)
13. Online Survey	Web-based forms used to collect information from various participants quickly and accurately, enabling fast analysis.	(United Nations, 2011)
14. Online Whiteboard	An online collaborative tool that allows multiple users to create, organise, and share visual content such as notes, diagrams, and drawings in real time (e.g., Miro, Mural).	(Tobin, 2006)
15. Podcast	Digitally recorded audio files that can be shared with colleagues, partners, and stakeholders for communication, learning, or information sharing.	(United Nations, 2011; Yuan et al., 2013)
16. Project Management Platform	A centralised collaboration web-based software for planning, managing, tracking and reporting projects (e.g., Asana, Trello, Smartsheet, Basecamp, Jira, Zoho Projects).	(Neuenfeldt, 2023)
17. Social Media	An online social networking service or site that allow people to communicate, create, share, and aggregate	(Steffen et al., 2017; Yuan et al., 2013)

Tool	Description (*)	Reference
	content (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube).	
18. Staff Directory	A searchable electronic resource that locates people (also called yellow/white pages) and provides contact information, roles, and details about employees' skills, expertise, experience, and interests within an organisation.	(Tobin, 2006; United Nations, 2011)
19. Video/Tele Conferencing	A tool that allows people in two or more locations to interact in real time via audio and/or video, enabling meetings, training, and collaboration without travel (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams, GoTo Meeting).	(Alhaji et al., 2013; Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014; Tobin, 2006; United Nations, 2011; Yuan et al., 2013)
20. Videos	A digital medium that captures visual and auditory content, often used for demonstration, education, or advocacy.	(United Nations, 2011; Yang, 2004)
21. Virtual Bulletin & Message Board	A digital noticeboard for posting announcements, reminders, and important organisational updates.	(Majewska & Szulczyńska, 2014)
22. Website	A collection of interlinked web pages hosted online to provide information, resources, or services to internal or external audiences.	(Alhaji et al., 2013; Steffen et al., 2017; Tobin, 2006)
23. Wiki	A collaborative software that allows multiple users to create, edit, and publish content on a website (e.g., Wikipedia, Confluence, MediaWiki)	(Neuenfeldt, 2023; United Nations, 2011; Yuan et al., 2013)

*) The descriptions were generated using the listed references above, [Cambridge Dictionary](#) and ChatGPT.

3.2 Measuring the Effectiveness of Knowledge Sharing

If managers recognise that knowledge sharing benefits both employees and the organisation and wish to reward knowledge sharing behaviours (KSBs), they must first evaluate and measure these behaviours. However, KSB is a difficult concept to measure. One of the main challenges in setting up measurement for knowledge sharing is identifying and evaluating it at an individual level, especially regarding tacit knowledge. For example, it is relatively easy to track contributions within an online knowledge sharing system; however, monitoring whether knowledge is shared in informal social situations, such as through face-to-face conversations, is far more challenging. (Ipe, 2003; Yi, 2009.)

KSBs can be measured by assessing the specific actions individuals take to disseminate work-related knowledge and expertise within an organisation, across various formal and informal channels. This typically involves identifying and categorising these behaviours and then using valid and reliable instruments and indicators. Similarly to Bartol and Srivastava (2002), Yi (2009) proposes measuring KSBs through four subsets:

- (1) *Written contributions* refer to employees sharing their ideas, information, and expertise through written documentation – rather than dialogue – such as contributing to organisational databases or submitting reports that support colleagues and the wider organisation.
- (2) *Organisational communications*, includes sharing knowledge in formal social interactions within or across teams, work units, departments or divisions – like work teams or project groups may have regular meetings for brainstorming or problem solving by seeking ideas from employees.
- (3) *Personal interactions*, including informal social interactions among individuals, such as chatting over lunch and giving help or information to one another, which are harder to monitor but reflect voluntary knowledge exchange.
- (4) *Communities of practice*, includes voluntary groups of employees who communicate on topics of their common interests in a non-routine, personal manner, primarily through informal social interactions and unstructured system.

Creating a set of measures—also called as metrics or indicators—requires careful consideration. Indicators can be qualitative (e.g., “enhanced collaboration”) or quantitative (e.g., “decreased time to complete service X”). Below are some commonly used indicators for measuring the effectiveness of knowledge sharing (Janus, 2016):

A. Intermediate-outcome indicators

- Improved collaboration among staff or between departments
- Established dedicated budget for knowledge and learning

- Established or adapted knowledge and learning governance
- Instituted incentive mechanisms for open peer learning
- Created or improved domestic and international partnerships
- Improved capabilities to conduct result-oriented and relevant knowledge sharing

B. Result indicators

- Scaled up solutions at the organisational level
- Replicated solutions domestically or internationally
- Improved service delivery
- Registered or implemented more innovations
- Gained efficiencies in core operations
- Achieved greater recognition of client's knowledge sharing capacity

4 Good Knowledge Sharing Practices

Effective knowledge sharing rests on the integration of structured processes, culturally grounded behaviours, and interactive practices that enable employees to exchange both tacit and explicit knowledge. Across the APPROACH project, the survey, workshop, and theoretical work revealed a set of good practices already used within partner organisations. These practices demonstrate that knowledge sharing is not merely a technical exercise but a deeply social and cultural phenomenon influenced by organisational norms, trust levels, leadership behaviour, and the everyday interactions between employees. The most successful practices support cross-team collaboration, strengthen shared understanding, and create an environment where employees feel both motivated and safe to contribute their knowledge.

4.1 Social and Collaborative Practices Across Partner Organisations

Across the APPROACH project, partner organisations combine digital tools and social, collaborative practices to support knowledge sharing in daily work. The survey and workshop findings show that neither technology nor interaction alone is sufficient; effective knowledge flow emerges when shared platforms are supported by routines that bring people together to interpret, refine and apply information.

Digital tools form the basic infrastructure for communication and documentation. In some partner contexts, these systems are used systematically with clear expectations, while in others their use is fragmented due to overlapping tools, unclear guidance or inconsistent documentation habits. The findings emphasise that the availability of technology does not automatically lead to knowledge sharing unless supported by shared practices and a culture of openness. Alongside digital infrastructures, partner organisations make extensive use of interactive and relationship-centred methods. Meetings are the most widely used and most highly valued practice across the consortium. They provide regular opportunities for discussion, alignment and clarification, enabling teams to build shared understanding. Training also plays a significant role, offering structured environments for developing common competencies and ensuring that essential information reaches all employees.

Workshops emerged as particularly effective for deeper knowledge exchange. They allow participants to compare experiences, co-analyse challenges and develop joint interpretations: activities that digital repositories alone cannot facilitate. Brainstorming sessions similarly support open-ended exploration and the articulation of tacit knowledge, though their use and structure vary across organisational

settings. Mentoring was identified in the survey as one of the most positively perceived practices, especially in contexts where employees benefit from personalised guidance. Whether formal or informal, mentoring strengthens trust and supports the transfer of experiential knowledge that is difficult to document.

Complementing these are practices such as lessons-learned discussions, case reflections and informal conversations, which help teams make sense of experiences and share situational information that rarely appears in formal documents. While the prevalence of these practices varies, together they highlight that knowledge sharing relies on both structured activities and everyday social interaction. Overall, the findings show that partner organisations depend on the interplay of digital tools and collaborative practices. Technology ensures access to information, while interaction gives it meaning and supports mutual learning. Despite differences across organisational contexts, a common pattern emerges: knowledge sharing is most effective when technical systems and human practices reinforce one another, enabling employees to build shared understanding and contribute to collective learning.

4.2 Cultural Factors Affecting Knowledge Sharing

The findings demonstrate that organisational culture fundamentally shapes the success of knowledge sharing practices. Trust, openness, psychological safety, and shared goals repeatedly emerged as decisive cultural enablers. In contexts where employees feel valued and respected, knowledge sharing is more natural and frequent. Conversely, cultures characterised by low trust, informal gatekeeping, or limited leadership engagement tend to experience knowledge hiding, fragmented communication, and inconsistent access to information.

The differences observed between partner countries illustrate how cultural dimensions influence practices. Organisations with established structures and open communication climates tend to facilitate more consistent knowledge flow. In contrast, organisations facing cultural barriers—for example, limited trust between colleagues, hierarchical communication norms, or reliance on informal networks—experience challenges in sustaining knowledge sharing, even when technical tools are available.

The workshop discussions highlighted that overcoming cultural obstacles requires leadership commitment, explicit encouragement of open dialogue, and recognition for collaborative behaviour. Teams must also cultivate reciprocity: employees are more likely to share when they perceive that others will do the same. Thus, culture is not simply a backdrop for practices but an active determinant of whether those practices succeed.

4.3 Recommendations Emerging from the Survey and Workshop

The survey and workshop together produced several recommendations that support the development of robust knowledge sharing practices:

1. Organisations should formalise and systematise their knowledge sharing activities. While informal practices are valuable, the workshop revealed that inconsistencies in documentation, unclear processes, and reliance on ad hoc communication can lead to information gaps. Establishing shared templates, standard documentation methods, and structured opportunities for reflection helps ensure continuity and accessibility.
2. Participants emphasised the importance of allocating dedicated time for knowledge sharing. Many employees reported that time pressures prevent them from engaging fully in collaborative activities. Integrating short knowledge sharing segments into meetings and regularising reflective sessions, such as lessons-learned discussions, can address this gap.
3. Organisations should provide clear expectations and guidance on how to use digital tools. Survey results indicated that tool overload and lack of clarity reduce efficiency. By defining which tools should be used for which purposes and offering targeted training, organisations can improve confidence and reduce fragmentation.
4. Both the survey and workshop highlighted the need to strengthen cultural enablers, particularly trust, recognition, and psychological safety. Leaders play a crucial role by modelling open communication, actively participating in collaborative practices, and recognising contributions. Public acknowledgement of knowledge sharing can reinforce positive behaviours and motivate employees who may otherwise hesitate to share.

Finally, organisations should adopt cross-team and cross-country collaborative practices that bring together individuals from different backgrounds. The APPROACH workshop demonstrated that shared activities help build mutual understanding, reduce cultural distance, and facilitate collective problem solving. Peer skill clinics, cross-functional workshops, and collaborative digital spaces are effective ways to support these goals.

4.4 Creating an Environment Where Knowledge Sharing Thrives

The combined findings from the APPROACH project make it clear that good knowledge sharing practices rely on both structural arrangements and cultural conditions. Mentoring, workshops, peer

skill clinics, and other collaborative methods form the practical backbone of knowledge exchange. Yet their effectiveness ultimately depends on trust, shared purpose, openness, and leadership support. By integrating structured processes with socially grounded and interactive practices, organisations create an environment where knowledge sharing becomes embedded in daily work and where employees contribute willingly to organisational learning and innovation.

5 Summing Up: Becoming a Knowledge Sharing Organisation

Becoming a knowledge sharing organisation is not simply about implementing tools or processes; it is a strategic and cultural transformation that requires leadership commitment, trust-based relationships, and structured practices that enable the free flow of ideas and expertise. Both the World Bank (Janus, 2016) framework, the APPROACH survey, and the recent workshop confirm that organisational culture is the most decisive factor in determining the success of knowledge sharing initiatives. There is no universal solution because practices must align with the organisation's values, structure and context.

5.1 Key Insights and Lessons Learned

The combined findings from the survey, workshop and literature review reveal that becoming a knowledge sharing organisation requires the alignment of structures, behaviours and technologies into a coherent and sustainable system. Survey results emphasise that organisational clarity, supportive leadership and shared goals are among the most influential enablers of knowledge sharing, particularly in contexts where these elements are already well established. The workshop findings reinforce this by illustrating how leadership commitment expressed through active participation, transparency and consistent expectations creates a visible and powerful signal that shapes employees' willingness to contribute their expertise and insights.

Across all data sources, a second central insight concerns the importance of structured and repeatable practices. Organisations that systematically integrate methods such as Meetings, Workshops, Brainstorming sessions, Mentoring, Training and Lessons Learned reviews tend to display more robust knowledge flows. The survey identifies these practices as among the most effective ways to exchange both tacit and explicit knowledge across teams and organisational boundaries. The literature further supports this by demonstrating how interactive and socially grounded methods strengthen interpersonal communication, enhance psychological safety and facilitate the transfer of tacit knowledge, often the most difficult but also the most critical form of organisational knowledge to capture.

Digital infrastructures also play an essential role in fostering knowledge sharing. Survey responses indicate that commonly used tools such as email, collaboration platforms and document management systems continue to serve as the backbone of knowledge exchange, while more specialised or creative tools remain underutilised. Workshop discussions highlight that the challenge is not only tool availability but also coherence and clarity: employees benefit most when organisations reduce tool

overload, articulate explicit norms for tool use and ensure that all employees have the competence and time to use these tools effectively.

A recurring insight across all sources concerns the centrality of organisational culture. Trust, reciprocity and psychological safety consistently emerge as decisive factors that determine whether knowledge is shared openly or withheld. The literature points to the risks of knowledge hoarding, hiding and sabotage in environments where trust is weak, recognition insufficient or workplace politics dominant. Workshop contributions echoed this, noting that in some contexts limited trust, informal communication patterns and lack of leadership support undermine opportunities for collaborative knowledge exchange. These findings underline that knowledge sharing is not merely a technical or procedural matter, but a deeply social and relational process.

The survey conducted across several countries also reveals a broad recognition of the value of knowledge sharing, yet persistent challenges remain. Trust and psychological safety are seen as essential enablers, although gaps continue to exist. Leadership commitment strongly influences success: organisations where leaders actively model openness and allocate resources score higher overall. In contrast, incentive systems were identified as the weakest enabler, highlighting the need to strengthen motivational mechanisms. Clear organisational goals that explicitly link knowledge sharing to strategic success help foster alignment and reduce silos.

The workshop results further emphasise the need for structured and interactive methods such as regular knowledge sharing sessions, mentoring and consistent use of templates to capture lessons learned while also revealing that creative techniques remain underused. Participants across contexts agreed that dedicating time for knowledge exchange during meetings is essential to make sharing a consistent practice rather than an ad-hoc activity.

To foster effective knowledge sharing, organisations must embed it into their culture. This means creating an environment where employees feel psychologically safe to share ideas without fear of criticism or negative consequences. Leaders play a critical role by modelling openness, admitting mistakes and encouraging dialogue. When leadership demonstrates that knowledge sharing is valued and linked to organisational performance, employees are more likely to participate actively.

Equally important is clarity. Organisations should define what knowledge sharing means in their specific context and communicate why it matters. Without clear expectations, sharing remains inconsistent and dependent on individual initiative. Recognition systems, both symbolic and financial, help reinforce positive behaviours and signal that contributions are valued. Peer-learning practices, such

as informal sessions where employees share what they have learned, help normalise knowledge exchange and integrate it into everyday work.

5.2 Challenges and Cultural Dimensions

Despite the many enablers identified, organisations simultaneously face significant challenges that complicate the development of a sustainable knowledge sharing culture. A first set of challenges relates to structural and procedural gaps. Workshop discussions revealed that in many contexts knowledge often circulates informally rather than through well-defined documentation processes or shared repositories. This leads to inconsistencies, inefficiencies and the loss of critical knowledge when individuals are absent or change roles. Survey findings support this observation, highlighting uneven perceptions of procedural clarity, insufficient incentives and limited time allocated for knowledge sharing activities.

Cultural and behavioural factors form a second major challenge. The literature emphasises that knowledge sharing is deeply rooted in social relationships and therefore vulnerable to issues such as trust deficits, lack of reciprocity, psychological ownership, selective knowledge networks and workplace politics. These dynamics can result in behaviours such as knowledge hoarding, hiding or even sabotage particularly when employees perceive knowledge sharing as a threat to their status, influence or job security. Workshop contributions offered concrete examples of such dynamics, including low levels of trust, limited cross-team communication and a tendency to withhold information due to cultural norms or perceived power imbalances.

The analysis also reveals notable variation across organisational and cultural settings, affecting how knowledge sharing is understood and enacted. Some environments demonstrate a relatively mature and structured approach supported by coherent processes and an open communication culture, while others show positive attitudes but lack systematic practices, clarity or leadership engagement. In some contexts, deeper systemic challenges such as low trust, weak leadership involvement and informal communication patterns further hinder the emergence of collaborative knowledge exchange. These differences underscore the need for context-sensitive strategies rather than assuming a one-size-fits-all approach.

In addition to these relational and structural barriers, organisations often struggle with recognising and valuing knowledge sharing behaviours. Knowledge hoarding and hiding remain common, frequently driven by unclear recognition systems, internal politics or the fear that sharing expertise may lead to

others misusing it or claiming ownership of ideas. Structural barriers, such as the absence of clear procedures and fragmented repositories, further hinder accessibility and continuity.

Survey results also point to an overreliance on traditional methods such as meetings and training, while creative or innovative techniques, such as structured ideation tools, remain rarely used. Digital tools present another challenge: although email and collaboration platforms are widely adopted and well-rated, more interactive tools such as online whiteboards and project management platforms receive lower evaluations, indicating limited integration into everyday work practices.

The comparison between survey findings and the theoretical framework highlights both convergence and gaps. The survey confirms the effectiveness of structured and interactive methods, workshops, training, meetings and mentoring consistently rank highest, while the literature stresses the importance of balancing formal and informal practices to foster richer knowledge flows. Both sources agree on the central role of a leadership-driven culture and systematic documentation. Furthermore, theoretical concerns regarding the risks of knowledge sabotage and hoarding are indirectly reflected in survey responses emphasising the need for trust, recognition and supportive organisational behaviour.

5.3 Reinforcing the Importance of Sustaining a Knowledge Sharing Culture

Developing a knowledge sharing culture is not a one-time initiative but a continuous, long-term organisational commitment. Findings across all data sources underline that sustaining such a culture requires coordinated effort, explicit leadership commitment and persistent investment in both people and processes. Knowledge sharing directly strengthens organisational innovation by enabling employees to combine and transform their expertise into new ideas, improved practices and more impactful research outcomes. Theoretical insights emphasise that an organisation's innovation capacity is closely tied to how effectively it mobilises the knowledge, skills and experiences of its workforce particularly through practices that support the exchange of tacit knowledge.

Organisations that consistently share knowledge also demonstrate greater resilience. Maintaining accessible documentation, shared repositories and collective memory reduces vulnerability to knowledge loss resulting from staff turnover, siloed teams or inconsistent communication patterns. This resilience is especially important in research-intensive environments where long-term continuity and effective knowledge transfer between projects and teams are essential.

The cultural benefits of sustained knowledge sharing are equally significant. Interactive methods such as mentoring, workshops and collaborative meetings not only enhance learning but also strengthen

interpersonal relationships, build trust and support a sense of shared purpose. Survey and workshop results indicate that employees consider these methods effective not just because they convey information, but because they create opportunities for dialogue, reflection and mutual understanding. Once embedded, these cultural dynamics form a self-reinforcing cycle: as trust increases, knowledge sharing becomes more frequent, and as sharing increases, trust deepens further.

To truly sustain a knowledge sharing culture, psychological safety and trust must be woven into the organisational fabric. Employees need to feel confident that sharing their ideas will not lead to criticism, misuse or the risk of others claiming their contributions. Leadership plays a pivotal role by modelling openness, allocating resources, recognising contributions and ensuring that knowledge sharing is valued rather than perceived as an optional or time-consuming extra task. Incentive structures, both symbolic and financial, are essential for integrating knowledge sharing into daily routines and ensuring it does not get pushed aside under time pressure.

Sustaining this culture also requires balancing formal structures with informal interactions. While repositories, guidelines and digital tools provide consistency and accessibility, informal exchanges, such as spontaneous conversations, coffee-break discussions or Lunch & Learn sessions, often spark creativity and strengthen interpersonal trust. These informal moments should be viewed as complementary to structured processes rather than as substitutes.

Ultimately, maintaining a knowledge sharing culture requires more than introducing new tools or offering occasional training sessions. It demands a long-term strategic vision, consistent leadership behaviour and the integration of knowledge sharing expectations into everyday organisational routines. When these conditions align, knowledge sharing becomes not an additional task but a natural, embedded and valued part of everyday work.

5.4 Strategic Recommendations for Building a Knowledge Sharing Organisation

The evidence gathered through the survey, workshop and theoretical analysis indicates several interlinked strategic priorities that organisations should address when aiming to strengthen and expand their knowledge sharing practices. Becoming a knowledge sharing organisation requires action on both cultural and structural levels, supported by clear leadership commitment and integrated everyday practices.

Figure 2 Knowledge Sharing Organisation

1. **Embed knowledge sharing into organisational culture:** Organisations should promote psychological safety and trust through leadership behaviours, peer-support mechanisms and clear communication. Leaders play a critical role by modelling openness, encouraging dialogue and linking knowledge sharing explicitly to organisational success. A culture grounded in trust, fairness and recognition reduces the risk of knowledge hoarding or withholding and supports the view of knowledge as a collective asset rather than individual property.
2. **Establish structured and repeatable processes:** Findings across data sources highlight the need for consistent procedures for capturing, sharing and applying knowledge. Integrating reflection, documentation and lessons-learned discussions into routine workflows helps ensure that knowledge exchange becomes a regular practice. In some countries, workshop participants noted that the absence of such structured methods hinders consistent knowledge flow demonstrating that even small procedural improvements can lead to meaningful change. Standard templates, meeting structures and shared routines strengthen clarity and reduce reliance on informal and inconsistent practices.
3. **Develop centralised and coherent knowledge repositories:** Fragmentation of information across multiple platforms or private storage locations emerged as a common challenge. Organisations benefit from centralised, user-friendly repositories supported by clear conventions for naming, storing and accessing documents. In some contexts, disciplined use of

shared spaces has significantly improved accessibility and reliability of organisational knowledge. Such repositories also ensure equitable access to information across teams and roles and create a durable foundation for organisational memory.

4. **Strengthen digital tool competence and coherence:** While organisations have access to numerous digital tools, survey results show challenges related to tool overload, inconsistent usage and insufficient training. Offering continuous, accessible support, such as short training sessions, onboarding packages or micro-learning materials, helps ensure that all employees can use tools effectively and confidently. Clear guidelines on tool purpose and usage bring coherence and reduce fragmentation. Expanding the adoption of interactive platforms can also support more dynamic, collaborative knowledge exchange.
5. **Diversify and enrich knowledge sharing methods:** Traditional high-impact practices such as workshops, mentoring and collaborative meetings should be continued and strengthened, while creative and innovative techniques should be used to stimulate fresh thinking and spark new ideas. Broadening the methodological toolkit helps engage different employee groups and encourages the sharing of both tacit and explicit knowledge. Organisations are encouraged to institutionalise innovation rituals, such as idea campaigns, hackathons or themed learning sessions, to embed experimentation and continuous learning into everyday work.
6. **Implement incentive and recognition systems:** Knowledge sharing must be valued and rewarded. Both symbolic and financial incentives can reinforce positive behaviours and ensure that knowledge sharing activities are perceived as integral rather than optional. Recognition also plays an important role in countering fears that knowledge might be misused or that contributions will go unnoticed, thereby supporting a more open and collaborative culture.

This strategy is designed not only for the organisations directly involved in the project but also for teams and institutions seeking to strengthen collaboration and innovation more broadly. By documenting practices, insights and evidence transparently, the strategy becomes a resource that others can adapt to their own structural and cultural contexts. Organisations are encouraged to engage in cross-organisational dialogue, benchmarking and shared learning to collectively advance knowledge-driven innovation and organisational resilience.

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